

**Investigating The Validity And Test-Retest Reliability
Of The Optojump Device In Comparison To Force
Plates During Jump Tests Within Female Football
Players**

Luke Murray

Supervisors:

Dr Mark Sanderson and Dr Antonio Dello Iacono

School of Health and Life Sciences.

*A thesis submitted in fulfilment of the requirements of the University of the
west of Scotland for the award of Master of Research (MRes).*

Abstract

Background: The Optojump is a practical and cost-effective alternative for assessing lower body power and RSI through jump tests like the CMJ and DJ. While it demonstrates excellent validity and reliability for CMJ metrics compared to force plates, its performance in assessing DJ metrics has shown conflicting results. Additionally, studies often lack diversity in participant pools, with limited female representation and an absence of female football players. Moreover, not all metrics measured by the Optojump have been thoroughly analysed compared to the force plates. **Objective:** The purpose of this research was to investigate the validity and test-retest reliability of the Optojump at assessing all CMJ and DJ metrics provided by the Optojump in comparison to force plates within female football players. **Methods:** Twenty-Six female football players (age: 23.8 ± 6.2 , height (cm): 164.8 ± 3.7 , mass (kg): 65.1 ± 6.3) playing in the first team or academy of a club competing in the top league of woman's football in Scotland were recruited to participate in the study. Participants performed three trials of both CMJ and DJ on two separate testing sessions separated by one week. The best trial from each jump on both testing sessions was used for analysis. **Results:** Small systematic bias was found between the Optojump and force plates within all CMJ and DJ metrics recorded by the Optojump, indicating marginal overestimations in jump metrics by the Optojump. However, the presence of proportional bias was not found. The Optojump device exhibited moderate test-retest reliability for DJH, DJ CT and DJ RSI (ICC=0.50-0.74) and good test-retest reliability for DJ FT (ICC=0.75-0.90). The CV% values for DJ CT and DJ RSI did not meet the criteria for excellent reliability (CV < 10%) although DJH and DJ FT fulfilled the classification criteria for excellent reliability (6.7% and 3.4%, respectively). The Optojump device provided good test-retest reliability for CMJH (ICC=0.89 (0.77-0.95)) and CMJ FT (ICC=0.89 (0.77-0.95)) with CV% values being defined as excellent (2.8% and 1.4%). **Conclusion:** The findings from the current study indicate that the Optojump may serve as a viable alternative to the force plates for measuring CMJH, CMJ FT, DJH and DJ FT but not DJ CT or DJ RSI. However, caution must be taken when interpreting these results as despite excellent ICC (ICC > 0.9) and very small CV values (CV < 2%) between devices, there was a presence of systematic bias reported in all CMJ and DJ metrics.

Table of Contents

List of Tables	5
List of Figures.....	6
List of Abbreviations.....	7
Acknowledgements	8
Chapter 1: Literature Review	9
1.1. Introduction.....	9
1.2. Performance Characteristics	10
1.3. Monitoring Tests.....	15
1.4. Measuring Equipment.....	17
1.5. Different Types of Validity and Reliability	19
1.6. Current Validation and Test-Retest Reliability of Optojump.....	20
1.7. Objectives	24
Chapter 2: Methodology	26
2.1. Experimental Design	26
2.2. Participants.....	26
2.3. Procedures.....	26
2.4. CMJ Procedure.....	27
2.5. DJ Procedure.....	27
2.6. Data Analysis	28
2.7. Statistical Analysis	29
Chapter 3: Results.....	30
3.1. DJ Validity	30
3.2. CMJ Validity	36
3.3. DJ Test-Retest Reliability	38
3.4. CMJ Test-Retest Reliability	39
Chapter 4: Discussion	40
4.1. Limitations and Future Research	48

4.2. Practical Applications	49
Chapter 5: Conclusion	51
References	52
Appendices	69
Appendix 1.1: Concurrent set up of Optojump and Force Plates	69
Appendix 1.2: Participant Information Sheet provided to all participants prior to commencement of trials (continued to page 67).....	70
Appendix 1.2 (continued): Participant Information Sheet provided to all participants prior to commencement of trials.	71
Appendix 1.2 (continued): Participant Information Sheet provided to all participants prior to commencement of trials.	72
Appendix 1.3: Informed Consent Form provided to all participants prior to commencement of trials.	73
Appendix 1.4: PAR-Q Form provided to all participants prior to commencement of trials (continued on to page 71).....	74
Appendix 1.4 (continued): PAR-Q Form provided to all participants prior to commencement of trials.	75
Appendix 1.4 (continued): PAR-Q Form provided to all participants prior to commencement of trials.	76

List of Tables

Table 1. Concurrent Validation of Optojump on DJ Metrics in Reference to Force Plates.....	30
Table 2. Concurrent Validation of Optojump on CMJ Metrics in Reference to Force Plate	36
Table 3. DJ CV% and ICC with 95% Upper and Lower CI	38
Table 4. CMJ CV% and ICC with 95% Upper and Lower CI	39

List of Figures

Figure 1. Descriptive Data of DJ Jump Height Measured Concurrently By The Optojump And Force Plates During Test Session 1 And 2.....	30
Figure 2. Bland-Altman Plot of Optojump vs Force Plates DJ Jump Height	31
Figure 3. Descriptive Data Of DJ Flight Time Measured Concurrently By The Optojump And Force Plates During Test Session 1 And 2.....	32
Figure 4. Bland-Altman Plot of Optojump vs Force plates DJ Flight Time.....	33
Figure 5. Descriptive Data of DJ Contact Time Measured Concurrently By The Optojump And Force Plates During Test Session 1 And 2.....	33
Figure 6. Descriptive Data of DJ Contact Time Measured Concurrently By The Optojump And Force Plates During Test Session 1 And 2.....	34
Figure 7. Descriptive Data of DJ Contact Time Measured Concurrently By The Optojump And Force Plates During Test Session 1 And 2.....	35
Figure 8. Descriptive Data of DJ Contact Time Measured Concurrently By The Optojump And Force Plates During Test Session 1 And 2.....	35
Figure 9. Descriptive Data of CMJ Jump Height Measured Concurrently By The Optojump And Force Plates During Test Session 1 And 2.....	36
Figure 10. Bland-Altman Plot of Optojump vs Force plates CMJ Jump Height	37
Figure 11. Descriptive Data Of CMJ Flight Time Measured Concurrently By The Optojump And Force Plates During Test Session 1 And 2.....	37
Figure 12. Bland-Altman Plot of Optojump vs Force plates CMJ Flight Time	38

List of Abbreviations

ACL	Anterior Cruciate Ligament
COM	Centre of Mass
CM	Centre Metre
CMJ	Countermovement jump
CMJH	Countermovement jump height
CMJ FT	Countermovement flight time
COD	Change of direction
DJ	Drop jump
DJH	Drop jump height
DJ CT	Drop jump contact time
DJ FT	Drop jump flight time
DJ RSI	Drop jump reactive strength index
FT	Flight Time
JH	Jump Height
KM	Kilometre
M	Meter
RFD	Rate of force development
RSI	Reactive strength index
SSC	Stretch-Shortening Cycle
TOV	Take off velocity
3D	Three-Dimensional
ICC	Intraclass Correlation Coefficient
CV	Coefficient of Variation
N	Number

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my gratitude to Dr. Mark Sanderson and Dr. Antonio Dello Iacono for their invaluable guidance and support throughout the entire process of completing this MRes thesis.

A sincere thank you is due to my family, friends, and colleagues for their continuous support and patience during the journey of completing this MRes thesis. Their encouragement and motivation played a pivotal role in helping me persevere through the challenges.

I express my thanks to all participants and external parties involved in the research; their collaboration was essential, and without them, the completion of this thesis would not have been possible.

Lastly, my appreciation goes to the technical team at UWS for their crucial support during the data collection phase. Their expertise and assistance were instrumental in the successful execution of this research.

Chapter 1: Literature Review

1.1. Introduction

During football matches players experience extensive physical demands, current literature proposes that female football players reach on average total distances of 10 kilometers (km) during match play (Martínez-Lagunas et al., 2014; Ramos et al., 2019; Sausaman et al., 2019), with high intensity running and sprinting accounting for between 22-28% of this distance (Vescovi and Favero, 2014).

Explosive actions such as jumping, accelerating, deceleration, sprinting and changes of direction (COD) are other common movement patterns which are frequently performed by players (Marcelino et al., 2016), with these actions potentially reaching 25 jumps, 423 accelerations, 430 decelerations and 500 change of directions (Mara et al., 2017, Yu et al., 2021), although variability exists with these figures due to different thresholds being set on monitoring devices during these tasks (Bradley and Vescovi, 2015). Explosive actions such as these demand near-maximal levels of strength and power production and the ability to repeat these actions in competition is key to success in sports such as football (Chelly et al., 2009; Dupont et al., 2004; di Salvo et al., 2007; Little and Williams, 2006; Haugen et al., 2013; Inklaar, 1994; McBride et al., 2006; Romero-Moraleda et al., 2021; Stolen et al., 2005). When performing these actions, the time available to produce force is very limited, meaning players must be trained to rapidly produce force at any given moment.

From a biomechanical standpoint power can be defined as the rate at which mechanical work is done, meaning it can be calculated as $\text{power} = \text{work}/\text{time}$ (Noffal and Lynn, 2012). When performing vertically orientated tasks such as jumping, the force necessary to oppose the force of gravity acting on the mass of the person/object moving, acts via displacement (considered the change of height in meters) during a defined time (in seconds). The result of force and displacement determines the work, which when divided by time results in power. The force applied to perform the vertically orientated task should also consider the acceleration used during the movement as well as the mass of the person/object. Therefore, another common way to define power is as the product of force and velocity. This concept of power production is what has led to the implementation of various training methods which manipulate force and velocity to develop an athlete's strength and power generating capabilities (Noffal and Lynn, 2012).

Maximal, explosive (Aagaard et al., 2002, Andersen and Aagaard, 2006) and reactive (Healy, Kenny and Harrison, 2018; Jarvis et al., 2022), or alternatively a combination of modalities are common training methods employed by practitioners looking to develop strength (Hughes et al., 2023). These training modalities produce neuromuscular adaptations in the form of improved musculotendinous stiffness, increased motor unit recruitment, coding (firing frequency), and synchronisation as well as

a reduction on neuromuscular inhibition. These adaptations will enhance the force that an athlete is capable of producing when performing tasks such as sprinting, jumping or COD (Suchomel et al., 2018) subsequently allowing for improved performance in these tasks. Lower body power and the rate of force development (RFD) have similarly been improved following a stage of explosive or maximal strength training (Aagaard et al., 2002, Maffiuletti et al., 2016, Comfort et al., 2022). Training-induced adaptations in RFD are thought to be achieved via developments in rapid muscle activation (Maffiuletti et al., 2016). The combination of improvement in the quantity of force that can be applied and the faster rate at which force can be produced at the earlier stages of muscle contraction are what resultantly improve sprinting and COD performance.

1.2. Performance Characteristics

Sprinting actions and quick changes of direction are considered prerequisites for successful performance in football (Haugen, Tønnessen and Seiler, 2013; Buchheit et al., 2014), as these actions are often required when scoring a goal (Faude, Koch and Meyer, 2012), evading an opponent and creating a shot on goal (Sweeting et al., 2017). Wisløff et al. (2004) established that increased power - as indicated through vertical jumping performance – strongly correlated to better sprint times during a 10-meter, 30-meter and 10-meter (m) shuttle run sprints in professional football players. Similarly, Altmann et al. (2018) found that across three seasons of professional football, players power was largely associated with a player's top speed. In a study by Barrera et al. (2023) lower body power was found to have a moderate correlation with 20m and 30m sprint time but not 10m in 33 elite level male football players. Findings which are similar to that of a previous study which evaluated 25 professional football players and finding correlations between lower body power – expressed via Countermovement jump (CMJ) - and 30m sprint performance but no relationship with 10m (Boraczyński et al., 2020).

It is possible to explain the correlation between lower body power and these actions by considering that both sprinting and jumping require significant amounts of vertical force applied to the ground in order for the body to accelerate vertically and horizontally (Colyer et al., 2018). However, it is essential to consider the test selection for measuring lower body power, as different jump tests significantly influence the representation of power. Vertical jumping tests are most commonly used as a representation of a player's power generating capabilities, however sprinting actions require not only vertically orientated power production but horizontal as well (Morin, Edouard and Samozino, 2011). These studies may have benefited from utilising a combination of vertical and horizontally orientated jump tests as a representation of power. Additionally, it must also be considered that sprinting is a multidimensional skill which does not only require efficient neuromuscular capabilities but also technical skill (Morin, Edouard and Samozino, 2011; Rabita et al., 2015). Regardless of the

fact, these studies provide a clear indication of the relationship present between lower body power and sprinting actions within football players. Although, the omission of female football players from the studies conducted by Wisløff et al. (2004), Altmann et al. (2018), and Barrera et al. (2023) limits the breadth of the review on the influence of lower body power on sprinting performance. By incorporating female participants, who have been shown to have different power generating capabilities than males (Jones et al., 2016), these studies would have allowed for a more comprehensive examination and could have shed light on any potential disparities in sprint performance between males and females at different distances. The disparity between male and female power generating capabilities was demonstrated by Suchomel et al. (2015) when examining differences in lower-body power measured via CMJ height between males and females, reporting females jump heights to differ by as much as 37.3% compared to males. The difference observed between male and female power production is accredited to males having a greater percentage of muscle mass than females (Beckham et al., 2019; Hoeger et al., 1990; Suchomel et al., 2015). In spite of the fact that both males and females develop muscle at the same rate, males develop more muscle mass and a greater percentage of fast-twitch muscle fibres, compared to their female counterparts (Laubach, 1976; Decker et al., 2003). This larger muscle mass, along with greater quantity of fast-twitch muscle fibers, allows males to display greater strength and power outputs than females, which resultantly provides them with an enhanced ability to perform movements requiring high power outputs such as accelerations and sprinting (Decker et al., 2003).

The ability to change direction at speed is essential for a player's capability to respond to tasks in different positions in the game, making this equally important to successful performance as speed (Brughelli et al., 2008; Mujika et al., 2009; Goral, 2015). Current research has found a relationship between lower body power – measured via CMJ performance - and COD speed within football players (Castillo-Rodríguez et al., 2012; Lockie, 2014; Lockie, Dawes and Jones, 2018). The exact mechanics of how lower body power improves COD speed is thought to be due to the enhanced ability at generating propulsive power both horizontally and vertically in the acceleration phase of the COD (Spiteri et al., 2013, 2015). This making the athlete more efficient at rapidly and systematically coordinating force and impulse application during the key phases of the movement - braking phase (eccentric), plant phases (isometric), and propulsive phase (concentric) (Morin, Edouard and Samozino, 2011). Lockie, Dawes and Jones. (2018) investigated the influence that lower body power, expressed via CMJ performance, has on COD speed within collegiate woman football players. A relationship was found between lower body power and 180° COD speed, with higher performing athletes performing better in the tests than their counterparts. Similarly, Emmonds et al. (2019) found a very strong relationship between CMJ, squat jump (SJ) and DJ height with COD ability

during a 5-0-5 test within elite female football players, highlighting the association between lower body power and COD speed. These similarities may be apparent due to the resemblance in the 180° COD task assigned to the participants.

On the contrary Kobal et al. (2021) studied the relationships between linear sprint, curve sprint, COD, and jump performances in elite female football players. They reported that CMJ performance was significantly correlated with linear sprint ($r=0.45$) and curve sprint performance ($r=0.56$), but not with COD performance ($r=0.21$). Failing to establish a relationship between COD and lower body power could in part be down to the test selection used for COD speed. A modified zig-zag test was used which utilise 100° COD's, incorporating different COD tasks would have provided a more meaningful analysis. Similarly, Nimphius, McGuigan and Newton. (2010) reported a very strong relationship with relative strength and COD ability within softball players ($r=-0.73-0.85$) but deemed vertical jump performance and COD ability separate athletic qualities in female softball players. Although this finding could in part be explained by the small sample size, the infrequency of vertical jumping tasks performed in the sport of softball in comparison to football (Nimphius, McGuigan and Newton, 2010), or even the time of the testing with respect to the participants current training cycle as factors such as accumulated fatigue may have negatively impacted the participants performance during the tests. Similar to sprinting performance, COD speed is understudied within female football meaning the body of evidence currently existing lacks reliability. Due to the scarce research, it is common for sports practitioners to apply evidence found in male participants to the female population. However, males have been found to perform better in COD tasks due to a more effective and rapid motor response as a result of their greater lower-body strength and power generating capabilities providing larger application of force and impulse (Nygaard, Rædergård and van den Tillaar, 2019), therefore the practical applications from male-orientated research may not transfer to female athletes.

When striving to improve performance in sprinting and COD tasks, it is vital to consider the influence of other contributing factors. Reactive strength, as a performance characteristic, possesses the capacity to exert a positive impact on a player's overall performance. Reactive strength refers to a player's capability to utilise their stretch shortening cycle (SSC), which involves the musculotendinous unit's ability to produce a rapid concentric contraction instantly following a rapid eccentric action (Cavagna, Saibene and Margaria, 1965; Nicol, Avela and Komi, 2006; Wilson and Flanagan, 2008). This occurs during movements in which the body is exposed to impact forces which create stretch. The magnitude of the impact force, a player's ability to endure such forces, and task-specific constraints collectively influence the nature of the SSC (fast ≤ 250 ms or slow > 250 ms). Examples of this can be observed in football-related tasks like accelerating, sprinting, jumping, and changing

direction (Komi, 2000; Turner and Jeffreys, 2010). Alterations in a player's reactive strength result from changes in the stretch rate (ability to execute eccentric and concentric muscle actions at a higher pace) or from variations in the stretch load (increased drop height during rebound-orientated jumping tasks). Therefore, reactive strength serves as a metric for gauging an athlete's capacity to rapidly produce force (e.g., explosiveness). Considering that football-specific movements are often time-constrained, evaluating these qualities proves valuable for creating exercise prescriptions and monitoring athletes.

The Reactive Strength Index (RSI) serves as a metric for quantifying a player's reactive strength and, by extension, their ability to efficiently utilise the SSC. RSI is assessed through explosive jump tests, such as the drop jump (DJ), wherein the participant drops off a predetermined-height box and rapidly rebounds off the floor, with the goal of minimising ground contact time and attaining maximum height in the process. RSI is then calculated by dividing jump height by ground contact time. On some occasions this will then be divided by 100, as is done when using certain equipment like the Optojump. Current literature has investigated the relationship between RSI and performance characteristics including speed, acceleration and COD speed (Young, James and Montgomery, 2002; Salonikidis and Zafeiridis, 2008; Tsolakis, Kostaki and Vagenas, 2010; Wilkinson et al., 2012; Lockie, 2014; Turner et al., 2016; Pehar et al., 2017; Furlong, Harrison and Jensen, 2021; Jarvis et al., 2022). Lockie. (2014) investigated the association between RSI and a composite of speed and COD tests in male field athletes. The results revealed moderate to large negative correlations with various performance metrics: 10 m sprint test ($r=-0.680$), 20 m sprint test ($r=-0.632$), 40 m sprint test ($r=-0.536$), multi-directional COD test-T Test ($r=-0.505$), and a COD and acceleration test ($r=-0.638$). Young, James and Montgomery. (2002) investigated the relationship between RSI and both acceleration and COD speed in male athletes participating in sports characterized by multiple changes of direction, such as football. Moderate to large negative associations were found between all variables tested, with RSI providing large associations with 8m acceleration ($r=-0.55$), 20° left COD ($r=-0.50$), 20° right COD ($r=-0.65$), 40° right COD ($r=-0.53$) and four 60° COD's ($r=-0.54$). Of note, only small negative correlations were found with 60° COD tasks which suggests that reactive strength has less of an impact with larger COD tasks, possibly because of the reduced ground contact time with smaller COD movements compared to larger, therefore utilising the SSC to a greater extent (Jarvis et al., 2022). The relationship observed between RSI and performance characteristics in male football players is consistent with findings in other literature investigating various sporting disciplines, such as squash (Wilkinson et al., 2012), fencing (Tsolakis, Kostaki and Vagenas, 2010, Turner et al., 2016), tennis (Salonikidis and Zafeiridis, 2008), basketball (Pehar et al., 2017), rugby (Furlong, Harrison and Jensen, 2021) and multiple more. However, in contrast to these findings, Northeast et al. (2019)

found that RSI had only a marginal predictive value for multidirectional speed among elite male footballers competing in the English Premier League. The larger degree of COD test involved in this study could in part explain these findings, as was similar with the findings from Young, James and Montgomery (2002). It is possible that larger COD tasks do not allow for the preservation of energy via elastic energy storage as is seen within shorter COD angles (Sheppard and Young, 2006; Brughelli et al., 2008).

Although the relationship between RSI and performance characteristics such as COD speed, acceleration and max velocity have been well documented, an overwhelming majority of this research has solely focused on male athletes. A small portion of the literature has investigated the relationship RSI has with these performance characteristics within female athletes (McCurdy et al., 2010; Barr and Nolte, 2011; Jones et al., 2016; Loturco et al., 2019). Of those that have only one study focusses on female football players, therefore warranting caution when interpreting the findings as there is a lack of scientific backing. McCurdy et al. (2010) found RSI to have no relationship with 10 m sprint time ($r=0.16$) and 25 m sprint time ($r=-0.02$) within Division 1 female football players from the National Collegiate Athletic Association (NCAA). However, the test selection for assessing RSI was a single leg DJ, where the average of both limbs was used to determine the RSI value. This contrasting with the more commonly utilised bilateral DJ test. The authors also included a single leg horizontal DJ test and averaged both limbs to get a RSI value, these findings demonstrated a moderate negative association with 25m sprint time ($r=-0.49$) but a small association with 10 m sprint time ($r=0.08$). The inclusion of the single leg horizontal DJ test demonstrates a small relationship between RSI and 25 m sprint time but does not provide a strong enough correlation to indicate RSI has a relationship with sprint time over 0-10 m. These findings could be explained by the relatively short distance of the tests selected for this research. Reactive strength may show stronger relationships with longer sprinting distances because of the necessity to generate forces in less contact time whilst at peak running velocity (ca. 0.1 s) compared to early acceleration (ca. 0.2 s) (Viitasalo et al., 1997). Although the 25 m test showed moderate associations, the 10m and 25m sprint tests used in this study might provide insufficient time for athletes to attain peak running velocity, meaning reactive strength will have had less of an impact. The incorporation of longer distances in sprint tests may have provided a more accurate representation of the relationship between RSI and sprint speed. Loturco et al. (2019) explored this association using longer sprint tests (40m, 60m), although the study recruited female long jumpers and sprinters, who possess different physical capabilities in comparison to football players. Nonetheless, the study revealed small to moderate negative correlations between RSI and longer sprint tests when RSI was calculated from a 45 cm vertical drop. Intriguingly, the authors also investigated this relationship with RSI calculated

from a 75 cm vertical drop, discovering larger correlations for all the performed sprint tests. This would suggest that vertical drop height may play an integral part in RSI value and therefore establishing relationships between RSI and other performance characteristics. Similar findings were observed in research conducted by Beattie et al. (2017) and Barr and Nolte (2011), where RSI was assessed using vertical drops ranging from 12 cm to 84 cm. Notably, varied associations were identified depending on the specific drop height utilised in the assessments. Jones et al. (2016) investigated the association between RSI and both sprint speed and COD speed in elite female rugby players. The results revealed a moderate negative relationship between RSI and various sprint distances, including 5 m, 10 m, 20 m, 30 m, and 40 m, as well as the speed in COD tests for both left and right directions ($r = -0.3$ to -0.45). From previous literature, it is evident that there is a relationship between RSI and both sprint and COD speed within the female athlete population, although the research conducted on this topic has been limited. Only one study has recruited female football players, therefore highlighting the importance of further research to allow for a better understanding of the relationship between RSI and performance in female athletes, particularly in football.

1.3. Monitoring Tests

Considering the significant impact that lower body power and RSI can have on performance, it is imperative to establish appropriate testing protocols. In existing literature, a diverse array of jump tests has been utilised to assess lower body power and RSI. The CMJ appears to be the most frequently implemented lower body power measurement test, as evidenced in a systematic review conducted by Sole et al. (2021) in which among the 26 studies implementing training programs to improve lower body power, 23 of them incorporated the CMJ as a pivotal measurement test. Whereas RSI requires a rebound action to determine the relationship between contact time and jump height, therefore DJ is the most frequently implemented testing protocol as evidenced in a systematic review by Jarvis et al. (2022) in which 31 of the studies included in analysis incorporated a variation of the DJ as their measurement test.

Beyond serving as a measure of lower-body power, the CMJ can also be utilised for various purposes, including monitoring neuromuscular fatigue and interpreting the effectiveness of specific training programs (Gathercole et al., 2015, Oliver, Lloyd and Whitney, 2015; Wong, Huang and Chen, 2020; Lombard et al., 2021; Silva et al., 2021). This jump test is particularly common within football players due to the performance test involving a rapid coupling of eccentric and concentric muscle contractions resembling that found in activities performed in football. Modern day football players experience heightened physical demands during match-play now more than ever, primarily due to shorter recovery periods between matches and an increase in neuromuscular load experienced

during a game (Barnes et al., 2014). The intensified physical demands in modern football have exacerbated post-match residual fatigue, indicating the requirement of extended recovery periods (Mohr, Krstrup and Bangsbo, 2005; Silva et al., 2013). Neuromuscular changes, including decreases in force production and power, along with impairments in physical performance such as sprint ability, are frequently reported in the acute days post-match (Girard et al., 2015; Hader et al., 2014; Magalhães et al., 2010). The magnitude of these effects increases within the initial 24 hours after, peaks between 24 and 48 hours and then subsides and returns to baseline after 72 to 96 hours (Ascensão et al., 2008; Ispirlidis et al., 2008; Magalhães et al., 2010).

The effectiveness of the CMJ test is evident within this context as it has been used as a monitoring tool to highlight the rate at which neuromuscular fatigue returns to baseline performance (Andersson et al., 2008; Robineau et al., 2012; Hoyo et al., 2016; Romagnoli et al., 2016). Andersson et al. (2008) found elite female football players CMJ performance to be diminished at 5, 21, 45, 51, and 69 hour time points after a match, similarly Romagnoli et al. (2016) found elite male football players CMJ performance to be impaired at 30 minutes, 24 and 48 hours after a match. To advance our understanding of neuromuscular recovery, future research should focus on employing consistent measuring timeframes for both male and female participants. This approach will facilitate a direct comparison and enable the identification of similarities and potential differences in the recovery processes between the two genders. It is important to consider that these studies focused on neuromuscular recovery after a single game. Given the variability in a game of football, influenced by factors such as the opposing team, the observed neuromuscular fatigue in one game may vary from another. Additionally, these studies used different measurement devices to assess neuromuscular fatigue. Andersson et al. (2008) utilised a criterion method force plate whereas Romagnoli et al. (2016) employed a portable force plate. The variation in measurement devices between these studies could potentially impact the findings reported, highlighting the need for further research specifically dedicated to assessing the validity of portable jump monitoring devices. The DJ test provides a relatively simple jump test which measures RSI, which is commonly used in intervention studies to establish associations with performance characteristics (Jarvis et al., 2022) and to assess the impact of different training techniques on RSI (Hamilton. D, 2009; Montalvo and Dorgo, 2019; Keller et al., 2020; Ramirez-Campillo et al., 2023). Besides from these purposes, the DJ test can serve as a screening procedure to evaluate neuromuscular control. This application is particularly prevalent within the rehabilitation setting for athletes recovering from anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) injuries. This has been evidenced in previous literature in which the DJ has been shown to have good inter and intra-rater reliability and high sensitivity at detecting risk factors associated with ACL injuries (Redler et al., 2016).

Considering the multi-purpose nature of the CMJ and DJ, as well as the frequency of these tests in current research, it is of significant importance that the measurement devices used to evaluate these tests are valid and reliable.

1.4. Measuring Equipment

Numerous devices exist for measuring jump height (JH) in the CMJ and DJ. The availability of different devices introduces the potential to employ varying methods in the calculation of these metrics. To date, force plates and 3 Dimensional (3D) motion tracking systems are considered the gold standard devices for calculating JH (Chiu and Dæhlin, 2020; Wade et al., 2022). These devices allow for force-time data and position time data to be captured and analysed to calculate JH (Chiu and Dæhlin, 2020; Wade et al., 2022). However, due to the impracticality and high cost associated with the 3D Motion tracking systems, force plates are generally the device utilised in a scientific research setting. Although force plates offer a more practical alternative to 3D motion tracking systems, their lack of portability and integration in laboratory floors presents limitations with the device. Additionally, their high cost has led to the development of more accessible and cost-efficient alternatives which offer similar results, such as contact mats (Stanton et al., 2019), Optical systems like the Optojump (Healy, Kenny and Harrison, 2016; Attia et al., 2017; Słomka et al., 2017; Montalvo et al., 2021), smartphone apps (Haynes et al., 2019), accelerometers (Watkins et al., 2020) and inertial measurement devices (Schleitzer et al., 2022). Devices such as these offer the possibility of instantaneous feedback on jump performance, emphasising their application in a practical setting.

Various methods have been employed in the calculation of JH including the flight time (FT) method, take-off velocity (TOV) methods, and double integration (Chiu and Dæhlin, 2020; Kozinc and Pleša, 2023). While these methods can be calculated using the gold standard force plates, some are also applicable to more practical and cost-effective alternatives, such as the Optojump. Within the current literature, the most frequently utilised methods for JH calculation seem to be the FT methods and TOV methods (Kozinc and Pleša, 2023; Xu et al., 2023). The FT method is underpinned by the fundamental kinematic laws of free fall. Assuming that the body alignment remains constant at take-off and touchdown the vertical distance achieved by the centre of mass (COM) is calculated using the following equation:

$$JH=FT^2/8 \times 9.81 \text{ ms}^{-2}$$

The most commonly used TOV method involves the vertical velocity of the COM at take-off (Moir, 2008). To determine the vertical velocity of the COM, the vertical force trace must be integrated using the trapezoid rule after normalizing the trace to the body mass. The integration process begins at the initiation of the jump and concludes at take-off. Subsequently, the calculated vertical velocity

of the COM at take-off can be employed in the following equation of uniform acceleration to compute the jump height (Moir, 2008):

$$JH = TOV^2 / 2g$$

When force plates are available, the TOV method is often preferred over the FT method because potential changes in body configuration during the jump do not impact the TOV method (Xu et al., 2023). For instance, flexing the lower limbs during the jump can extend the FT and artificially inflate the calculated JH in the FT method (Kibele, 1998). In contrast, the TOV method remains unaffected by such movements during the jump. Although it is crucial that the calculation of JH via these methods is done carefully as factors such as data filtering (Pinto and Callaghan, 2021) and detection thresholds (Pérez-Castilla et al., 2021) make them sensitive to the detection of take-off and touchdown.

With these two methods JH is calculated as the distance travelled by the body's COM from the instance of take-off to the peak of the jump (Aragon-Vargas, 2000; Linthorne, 2001). A notable limitation of these methods is that COM is already elevated before the take-off, mainly due to the plantarflexion of the ankle (Chiu and Dæhlin, 2020; Wade et al., 2022), therefore leading to underestimations of JH. The degree of this underestimation can be affected by several factors such as foot length and lower limb configuration (Kozinc and Pleša, 2023). This has led to consideration of other methods to calculate JH which may provide a more accurate representation. When utilising the force plates, the forward double integration method is a possible alternative approach which may be more accurate. In this method, velocity data is reintegrated to acquire displacement (Dias et al., 2011). JH is then considered as either the peak value of the vertical COM displacement, relative to the standing position, or the displacement obtained before the jump is added to the displacement provided by the TOV or FT method (Kozinc and Pleša, 2023). This method has been proven to have very good agreement with 3D motion tracking method for countermovement jump height (CMJH) (Dias et al., 2011; Wank and Coenning, 2019).

When force plates are not readily available to practitioners, a variety of approaches can be adopted to determine JH. Namely the utilisation of field-based testing equipment such as smartphone applications, contact mats or the Optojump which use the FT method. These have been used in practical applications when assessing training interventions (Markovic, 2007; Hackett et al., 2016) and neuromuscular fatigue and muscle damage (Claudino et al., 2017; Romero-Parra et al., 2021). Therefore, as long as practitioners consistently employ the FT method, the jump heights obtained will offer a reliable estimate of an individual's progress or performance decrements. Given the practicality of field-based testing equipment and the positive research around the FT method, it is of

crucial importance that the field-based testing equipment employed to assess JH is valid and has good test-retest reliability. A particular device which has been tested for validity and test-retest reliability is the Optojump device. However, there is scarce research on this area for all metrics during both the CMJ and DJ. Of the research which has investigated the validity and test-retest reliability of the Optojump, there has been very similar participants recruited. The integration of the Optojump device within the female football population has the potential for positive contributions for the sport. However, prior to its implementation, it is imperative that it be thoroughly examined in terms of its validity and test-retest reliability within this specific participant pool.

1.5. Different Types of Validity and Reliability

Validity can be described as the degree to which a test or measurement accurately assesses the specific concept it is attempting to assess (Kamper, 2019). In research, various forms of validity can be used, such as content validity, face validity, construct validity, and criterion validity (Setia, 2017). Among the various types of validity employed in sport science research, construct validity and criterion validity are particularly prevalent. Construct validity refers to the extent of which a test or instrument accurately measures the theoretical construct it is intended to assess (Barten et al., 2012). Criterion validity refers to the effectiveness of one measure in predicting an outcome based on another measure (Manz et al., 2022). This can be divided into predictive validity, which assesses the extent to which a test predicts future performance, and concurrent validity, which evaluates the correlation between a test and an existing measure, where both are often recorded simultaneously (Wainer & Sireci, 2004). Construct and concurrent validity demonstrate similarities, as one method to establish construct validity involves comparing a measure to the “gold standard,” as is seen in concurrent validity. In the context of assessing jump height, where the force plates are considered the gold standard, concurrent validity serves as an appropriate approach for investigating the validity of alternative devices, such as the Optojump (Chiang et al., 2015).

Reliability refers to the consistency of a measurement to perform its intended function, or produce repeatable results, over time (Chiang et al., 2015). This may suggest the extent to which a measurement is free from error. Similar to validity, there is several types of reliability and can be tested under different circumstances. These include test-retest reliability, inter-rater reliability, internal consistency reliability (Babu & Kohli, 2023; Chiang et al., 2015). Inter-rater reliability is defined as a measure of consistency and agreement between independent observers or assessment tools (Chiang et al., 2015). Internal consistency reliability refers to the degree of which various items within a single test consistently measure the same concept or construct. This form of reliability ensures that a test remains stable and cohesive across its individual components (Chiang et al., 2015). Test-retest reliability evaluates the consistency of a measure obtained from the same person

on two separate occasions. A high test-retest correlation between the two sets of results signifies strong test-retest reliability (Babu & Kohli, 2023; Chiang et al., 2015). However, several factors can influence reliability testing and must be carefully considered and controlled as much as possible. These factors include participant-related variables (such as fatigue, motivation, and mood), sample size (with smaller samples potentially leading to less precise results), and the time interval between testing sessions in a test-retest reliability design. Within the context of assessing the ability of a device to measure jump height consistently and accurately, test-retest reliability serves as an appropriate approach that offers a robust statistical support

1.6. Current Validation and Test-Retest Reliability of Optojump

In the existing literature examining the validity and test-retest reliability of the Optojump in assessing metrics involved in the CMJ and DJ, conflicting results have been reported. Nevertheless, the general consensus suggests that, during the CMJ, the Optojump demonstrates good validity and test-retest reliability in the metrics of Countermovement Jump Height (CMJH) and Countermovement Jump Flight Time (CMJ FT), albeit with the presence of small systematic bias (Glatthorn et al., 2011; Castagna et al., 2013; Słomka et al., 2017; Rago et al., 2018; Condello et al., 2020; Montalvo et al., 2021). Conversely, in the metrics associated with the DJ, the Optojump exhibits mixed validity and test-retest reliability, accompanied by the continued presence of marginal systematic bias (Healy, Kenny and Harrison, 2016, Condello et al., 2020; Montalvo et al., 2021).

Of the research that has investigated the CMJ metrics, all studies have demonstrated the Optojump to have good validity and test-retest reliability. Research conducted by Glatthorn et al. (2011) found there to be a presence of systematic bias as demonstrated by a -1.00 centre meter (cm) underestimation of the Optojump in comparison to Force plate measurements. Furthermore, the magnitude of differences between measurement devices was observed to escalate with increasing CMJH, suggesting the presence of proportional bias. Although with the high intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC) values (ICC=0.998) between the measurement devices being reported, and the minimal presence of systematic bias, the authors considered the Optojump a valid measure of CMJH. However, caution is advised when using the Optojump for CMJH assessments interchangeably with the force plates, and the authors suggest the inclusion of a correction equation if interchangeability between the two devices is desired. Additionally, it is important to note that the participants recruited in this study were exclusively males, therefore limiting the scope of this research to only be applicable within this gender. This study aligns with the work conducted by Montalvo et al. (2021), where the findings indicated excellent validity (ICC=0.94, Coefficient of Variation (CV)=7.95%) for the Optojump, accompanied by a very small degree of systematic bias. The absence of proportional bias in the Optojump's CMJH metric further reinforces the validity of the Optojump. In accordance with

these results, Słomka et al. (2017) found an almost perfect association with the force plates ($r=0.99$) and the presence of small systematic bias as demonstrated through an underestimation in CMJH in the Optojump. These studies indicate that the Optojump provides a valid measure of CMJH in comparison to the force plates however a small degree of systematic bias appears to be present between the devices. The research by Montalvo et al. (2021) is of particular importance as it is one of the select few that recruited female participants. While valuable, it is worth noting that the research does not exclusively focus on females, and among those recruited, participants were not athletes.

There is a scarcity of research conducted investigating the validity of the CMJ FT metric as well as CMJH. It is possible that the authors have optionally not reported these findings as the Optojump uses the CMJ FT to calculate CMJH. Regardless, it would be beneficial to incorporate the findings of CMJ FT along with the CMJH to provide a more comprehensive evaluation of the Optojump. Castagna et al. (2013) reported the Optojump to record the presence of systematic bias as demonstrated by lower (1.27%) CMJ FT values when compared to the force plates. However, Castagna et al. (2013) reported a nearly perfect association ($r=0.99$; 95% CI 0.098–0.99; $p < 0.0001$) between the measurement devices assessment of CMJ FT, therefore providing strong support for the concurrent validity of the Optojump in detecting CMJ FT. Further research is needed to corroborate the findings regarding CMJ FT displayed in this study. Furthermore, considering that Castagna et al. (2013) focused only on male participants, it is essential to conduct additional research to determine whether similar outcomes are observed in female football players.

Previous literature has found there to be excellent test-retest reliability of the Optojump compared to force plates, however the lack of variability amongst participants recruited warrants caution when interpreting findings (Cormack et al., 2008; Glatthorn et al., 2011; Attia et al., 2017; Słomka et al., 2017; Montalvo et al., 2021). Glatthorn et al. (2011) found the Optojump to have excellent test-retest reliability (ICC=0.989 (0.973–0.996), CV=2.2%) for CMJH within physically active male participants. Likewise, Cormack et al. (2008) reported excellent test-retest reliability for CMJH and CMJ FT (CV=5.0% and 3.3%, respectively) in the Optojump compared to force plates among male Australian League Football players. However, it is essential to exercise caution in interpreting these findings due to the relatively small number (n) of participants ($n=15$) in the study. Despite the promising reliability demonstrated within the specified context, further research with larger and more diverse participant pools would be beneficial to enhance the robustness and applicability of these findings in broader athletic settings. Montalvo et al. (2021) briefly broadened these findings by reporting excellent test-retest reliability for CMJH (ICC=0.98 (0.97–0.99), (CV=8.14% (6.14–10.22)) in the Optojump device amongst male and female participants with experience in plyometric training. The significance of

these findings lie in their inclusion of female participants, however, the male and female results being grouped in their analyses therefore present an issue when looking to interpret the findings of females exclusively. However, caution must be taken when interpreting these findings as although excellent ICC values are reported, the CV=8.14% suggests that there is still a large degree of variability between measurement devices. Although CV < 10% is generally accepted, there is potential call for reevaluating this as in many cases 8% variability would exceed the smallest worthwhile change (SWC) of interest. Słomka et al. (2017) furthered the work by Montalvo et al. (2021) by reporting excellent test-retest reliability (ICC=0.98 (0.958–0.991), CV=0.20%) within physically active males and female volleyball players. Although no specific analyses was completed on the CMJ FT metric in previous research, considering the Optojump utilises FT to calculate JH it could be expected that CMJ FT demonstrated excellent test-retest reliability as well. However, future research is required to collaborate this hypothesis.

The validity of the Optojump at assessing different DJ metrics in comparison to force plates has received less analysis in comparison to the CMJ (Healy, Kenny and Harrison, 2016; Montalvo et al., 2021). However, of the research that has investigated this topic there has been conflicting results. Healy et al. (2016) reported the presence of small systematic bias in DJ FT ($-0.004 \text{ s} \pm 0.002$), DJ Contact time (DJ CT) ($0.004 \text{ s} \pm 0.002$), and DJ RSI (-0.05 ± 0.04). As well as the presence of proportional bias between the Optojump and force plates during DJ CT, FT and RSI, indicating that the error between the devices generally increases as the magnitude of the measure increases. However, near perfect ICC values were reported between measurement devices for DJ FT (ICC=0.995 (0.992-0.997)), DJ CT (ICC=0.989 (0.982-0.993)) and DJ RSI (ICC=0.985 (0.973-0.997)), therefore suggesting that despite small underestimations in DJ FT, DJ RSI and small overestimations in DJ CT, the Optojump provided a valid measure of performance in these metrics in comparison to the force plates, however caution should be taken when a measurements are of a greater magnitude as the proportional bias between devices may affect the accuracy of the measurement. Interestingly, research by Montalvo et al. (2021) similarly found near perfect ICC values (ICC=0.94 (0.92–0.96) and low CV values (CV=7.11% (5.38–8.49)) between measuring devices for DJH. However, the degree of systematic bias between the studies differed, Montalvo et al. (2021) reported systematic bias in DJH (1.39cm (-3.18 to 1.17)) and DJ RSI (-0.24 (0.19 to 0.29)), therefore indicating the Optojump overestimates DJH and underestimates RSI. Whereas in the work by Healy et al. (2016) DJ RSI and DJ FT – which is used in the calculation of DJH – was underestimated. The most common reason for the underestimation has been accredited to the physical design of the Optojump, however the conflicting findings between these studies suggest other factors must be involved, although future research is required to collaborate this. Montalvo et al. (2021) reported that the Optojump may

exhibit reduced validity in measuring DJ RSI, as evidenced by CV values significantly surpassing the designated accepted threshold of CV <10%. Additionally, although ICC values, were classified as good (ICC=0.89), concerns are raised regarding the overall validity of the Optojump for this specific metric given the high CV% of 37.69%. Furthermore, a notable proportional bias was present in the DJ RSI measurement obtained from the two measurement devices. However, the grouping of male and female results for analysis, coupled with the non-consideration of athletic females as participants, In alignment with prevailing literature, Healy et al. (2016) exclusively focused on male participants in their study. Whereas Montalvo et al. (2021) recruited both male and female participants, weakening the study's capability to provide meaningful insights into the validity of the Optojump device compared to force plates specifically within the context of female football players. Consequently, the applicability of the findings to the female athlete population, particularly in the sport of football, remain limited. This is of particular importance as existing studies have highlighted the differences between male and female participants. Specifically, females tend to exhibit lower DJH and RSI values compared to their male counterparts (Addie et al., 2019; Höög and Andersson, 2021; Rubio-Peirotné et al., 2021). Several biomechanical factors contribute to these observed differences, including greater knee valgus throughout the DJ landing phase in post-pubescent females (Herrington and Munro, 2010; Haines et al., 2011; Arundale et al., 2020) and less knee flexion at the impact of DJ landing (Prieske et al., 2015; Chun et al., 2021). These biomechanical faults could potentially impede performance in the DJ for females. Additionally, the discrepancies in DJ characteristics may be influenced by variations in anthropometrics. Males are biologically predisposed to possess more muscle mass relative to body mass, providing them with a greater capacity to generate concentric impulse, subsequently leading to improved jump height. The fact both Healy et al. (2016) and Montalvo et al. (2021) found proportional bias in some DJ metrics it suggests that as the magnitude of the measurement increases, the ability of the optojump to accurately measure this decreases. As it is shown that females are unable to achieve a similar magnitude of measurements in the DJ compared to males, then it may be possible that proportional bias is not present in a female population. However, future research is required to collaborate this.

Previous literature has primarily focussed on investigating the test-retest reliability of the Optojump at assessing specific DJ metrics, such as DJH and DJ RSI. There is a notable gap in the literature concerning a comprehensive examination of the test-retest reliability of the Optojump compared to force plates across all the DJ metrics the device measures. This gap becomes increasingly pronounced when the inclusion criteria includes female athletes. Therefore presenting issues for practitioners and researchers interested in utilising the Optojump in research incorporating female athletes, as the current body of evidence may not adequately capture the reliability of the device for

this specific demographic and the full range of metrics it assesses. Closing this research gap is essential for establishing a more thorough understanding of the Optojump's test-retest reliability across various metrics and participant groups. Of the research investigating this topic, there has been mixed findings reported (Condello et al., 2020; Montalvo et al., 2021). Montalvo et al. (2021) investigated the test-retest reliability of the Optojump, presenting this in the form of relative (ICC) and absolute (CV%) reliability measures. In the metric of DJH, their findings demonstrated excellent relative reliability (ICC=0.94 (0.90–0.97)). However, the CV values for the Optojump DJH failed to meet the acceptable criteria for excellent absolute reliability (CV=12.04% (8.59–15.48)). In similar fashion, the authors reported the Optojump to have excellent test re-test relative reliability for DJ RSI (ICC=0.96 (0.93–0.97)) but failed to meet the criteria for excellent absolute reliability (CV=19.9%, 95% CI: 15.22–24.58). Within this particular study by Montalvo et al. (2021) the authors did not specifically report DJ FT or DJ CT. It is plausible to assume that similar results would have been found in the DJ FT metric due to this being an underlying component of how the Optojump calculates. However, considering the involvement of DJ CT in the calculation of DJ RSI, failure to report this metric prevents a comprehensive assessment of the Optojump's reliability being conducted. Similar findings were found in work by Condello et al. (2020) which investigated the reliability of the Optojump at assessing CT during lateral jumping and change of direction tests. Findings from the study revealed moderate-good relative reliability across all jump modalities (ICC=0.69-0.89). However, the Optojump did not meet the criteria for excellent absolute reliability in any jump modality metrics (CV>10%). Despite the use of a different jumping modality than is usually investigated, the test-retest reliability of the Optojump's measurement of CT remains consistent with the other metrics. Poor test-retest reliability in these metrics compared to that of the CMJ could potentially be down to the complexity of the jump. As the DJ is a more technically challenging jump, the execution of the jump may have been altered between testing sessions contributing to the low ICC values and high CV% reported in the research. Additionally, variations in participants motivation on different testing sessions might influence these results. Furthermore, training load between the testing sessions could impact on results as fatigue following training or a match will negatively affect the jump performance in the testing sessions.

Although a small portion of work has been done, the conflicting findings regarding the magnitude of validity and reliability of the device as well as the lack of female football players being involved in studies warrants future research to bridge this gap.

1.7. Objectives

The Optojump has been demonstrated to have excellent test-retest reliability in comparison to force plates when measuring CMJ metrics. However, conflicting findings have been reported in its

concurrent measurement of DJ metrics. Additionally previous research has demonstrated the presence of varying magnitudes of systematic bias in the Optojump compared to force plates when measuring CMJ and DJ metrics. Although, there has been conflicting findings regarding proportional bias present between the CMJ and DJ measurements assessed concurrently by the Optojump and force plates. Although research in this area is generally limited, most existing studies have predominantly recruited male participants. The few studies that have included female participants have mainly recruited from non-athletic females. The lack of female participants, in particular female football participants, warrants caution when interpreting the results as the findings from male participants may not be applicable to female participants. Such reasons for this include their poorer CMJ and DJ performance in comparison to their male counterparts. The lesser results in these jumps means the magnitude of measurements the Optojump is exposed to is lesser in females compared to males, possibly demonstrating the absence of proportional bias. Furthermore, no research has investigated the validity and test-retest reliability of all CMJ and DJ metrics measured by the Optojump in comparison to force plates. Therefore, the purpose of this research was to investigate the concurrent validity and test-retest reliability of the Optojump in comparison to force plates at assessing all CMJ and DJ metrics measured by the Optojump within female football players.

Chapter 2: Methodology

2.1. Experimental Design

This study employed a correlational study design aiming to investigate the validity and test-retest reliability of the Optojump compared to the criterion method using force plates. Participants reported to the Biomechanics Laboratory at the University of the West of Scotland on two separate occasions one week apart. Both sessions included the same procedures consisting of a CMJ and a DJ which were measured concurrently by the Optojump (Optojump, Microgate, Bolzano, Italy) and force plates (Appendix 1.1). Testing sessions were administered on MD-3/MD+4 to mitigate the effects of fatigue on participants performance.

It has been suggested that for unloaded jumps such as the CMJ no familiarisation is needed (Moir et al., 2004). However, given the complex nature of the DJ, and the fact that jump technique is a limiting factor in performance, familiarisation sessions were given to participants over a 4-week period prior to engaging in the study to eliminate improvement in technique effecting reliability. This was implemented through conditioning programmes containing both CMJ and DJ exercises into participants regular gym sessions. This included providing feedback on their technique and execution of their jump.

2.2. Participants

Twenty-Six female football players (age: 23.8 ± 6.2 , height: $164.8\text{cm} \pm 3.7$, body mass: $65.1\text{kg} \pm 6.3$) participated in the testing sessions. Inclusion criteria were: 1) currently playing in a first-team or youth academy team competing in a professional league (elite status), 2) ≥ 16 years of age, 3) being free from spine deformities and joints pain and, 4) not having musculoskeletal injuries for the past 6 months which had prevented them from training and exercising normally.

Participants were approached by the lead investigator and given a presentation regarding the study along with a study information sheet (Appendix 1.2). The lead practitioner was employed within the participants football club although it was emphasised that participation in the study was on a voluntary basis and that no negative consequences would arise from their refusal to participate. This research was approved by the University of the West of Scotland (UWS) Health and Life Science Ethics Committee.

2.3. Procedures

Participants reported to the Biomechanics Laboratory on two separate occasions, with each session being separated by a week. The force plates and Optojump systems were set up to allow for concurrent measurement of jump performance to take place. In the first session, participants were

provided with a consent form (Appendix 1.3) and PAR-Q (Appendix 1.4). Then, were assigned to a randomised order of jumps (1-CMJ, 2-DJ), which was computer generated prior to their arrival. Upon completion of this and after verbal discussions regarding any questions, participants had their anthropometric measurements collected – height (cm) using a stadiometer (Seca 213 Stadiometer), body mass (kg) using electronic scale (Seca 803 Clara Digital Personal Non-Medical Scale), both to 1 decimal place. Then, a standardised warm up was performed consisting of 5 minutes on a WattBike at 50 watts (W) and self-selected RPM, a series of dynamic stretches of the lower extremities and 5 sub-maximal trials of both the DJ and CMJ. Before commencing the jump tests participants were asked to position themselves on the centre of the Force plate to allow for calibration and offset voltages to be processed.

2.4. CMJ Procedure

Participants performed 3 maximal trials of the CMJ with 2 minutes of rest between trials to allow for optimal recovery. Jump instructions remained consistent for all individuals, these were to keep the arms akimbo (Buckthorpe, Morris and Folland, 2012; Castagna et al, 2013; Eagles et al, 2016; Ebben and Petushek, 2010), to squat down to a self-selected distance before explosively rebounding back up into a vertical jump with the intention of maximising the jump height, to keep your lower limbs straight in the air bone phase. Participants were reminded that if the following procedure was performed incorrectly then a 1-minute resting period would commence before partaking in another attempt for that trial.

Participants were provided with verbal encouragement during every jump, and data from both the Optojump and force plates was safely processed and stored to be used for analysis following completion of the session. To eliminate any potential impact of increased motivation on the results, participants were not provided with any feedback on their jump metrics throughout the testing procedure.

2.5. DJ Procedure

Participants performed 3 maximal trials of the DJ with 2 minutes of rest between trials. DJ box height was set at 0.3m, following previously established protocols (Ebben and Petushek, 2010; Haynes et al, 2019; McMahon et al, 2018), and the box was positioned approximately 10-15 cm behind the measurement devices (force plates and Optojump) and marked with tape to ensure positioning remained consistent between-subject trials. Jump instructions remained consistent for all individuals, these were to keep the arms akimbo (Buckthorpe, Morris and Folland, 2012; Castagna et al, 2013; Eagles et al, 2016; Ebben and Petushek, 2010), step off of the bench onto the middle of the Force plate and Optojump. Upon landing squat down to a self-selected distance before explosively

accelerating back up into a vertical rebound jump with the intention of minimising ground contact time and maximising jump height. Whilst in the air keep your lower extremities straight and not in flexion. Participants were reminded that if the following procedure was performed incorrectly then a 1-minute resting period would commence before partaking in another attempt for that trial.

Participants were provided with verbal encouragement during every jump, and data from both the Optojump and force plates was safely processed and stored to be used for analysis following completion of the session. To eliminate any potential impact of increased motivation on the results, participants were not provided with any feedback on their jump metrics throughout the testing procedure.

2.6. Data Analysis

During the warm-up routine participants anthropometric measurements were input in the Optojump software in preparation for starting testing. Data gathered from the Optojump software was exported and analysed using Microsoft Excel. Data gathered from the force plates was processed using the Bioware system and exported on to excel for data analysis. JH (cm) and FT (s) were taken from the participants CMJ. JH (cm), FT (s), CT (s) and RSI were taken from the DJ. JH from the force plates was calculated using the FT method to maintain consistency with the method applied by the Optojump. FT was interpreted after identifying the take-off and touchdown phase of each jump. This was attained by setting a threshold of force equal to five times the standard deviation (SD) of flight force (when the Force plate is unloaded), taken over a 300-ms period of the flight phase. This has been successfully utilised in recent work to identify take-off and touchdown phases (McMahon et al., 2017, 2018; McMahon, Rej and Comfort, 2017). This method was used instead of setting absolute threshold cut-off points as thresholds of 6 and 10 newtons (N) have been shown to lead to 1 and 1.5% overestimation in jump height, respectively (Street et al., 2001). Jump height on the Force plate was then derived from this flight time data using the equation from (Bosco et al, 1983).

$$JH = (9.81 \times FT^2 / 8)$$

RSI was calculated via the same equation as is used by the Optojump.

$$\text{Jump Height/Contact Time}/100$$

The best jump trial recorded on the Optojump was used for analysis, as well as the corresponding trial from the Force plate. The Optojump outputs were used to determine which trial was the best rather than the force plates, as the Optojump was the device under investigation.

2.7. Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics were presented using means and SD. A Shapiro–Wilk test was used to check the data normality. In line with previous work, validity of the Optojump device was examined using ICC (two-way random agreement model) with 95% confidence intervals (CI), CV and Bland-Altman plots, these assessed the level of agreement between the force plates and Optojump device by plotting the measurement differences (systematic bias) of all DJ and CMJ metrics against the respective means (Healy et al., 2016; Koo and Li, 2016). Test-Retest reliability of the Optojump system was examined using ICC (two-way random agreement model) with 95% CI, CV% with 95% CI, CV (unit) and Smallest Worthwhile Change (SWC).

ICC was interpreted as >0.90 (excellent), 0.75-0.90 (good), 0.50-0.74 (moderate), 0.26-0.50 (fair) and ≤0.25 (poor) (Portney and Watkins, 2009, Koo and Li, 2016). CV was interpreted as excellent if less than 10% (CV <10%) as recommended by previous studies (Atkinson and Nevill, 1998; Cormack et al., 2008 Haynes et al., 2019; Montalvo et al., 2021).

A two-way random agreement model was used for reporting ICC values based previous work (Atkinson and Nevill, 1998; Healy et al., 2016; Koo and Li, 2016), which suggests if results are going to be generalized to individuals with the same characteristics as the participants in the study, then this is an appropriate model to use. CV% was calculated using the within-subject, across test-retest approach by dividing the SD by the mean and then multiplying it by 100 and represented as a percentage. CV represented as a unit was calculated by dividing the mean by 100 then multiplying this by the CV%. SWC was calculated by multiplying the SD by 0.2. CV (unit) and SWC were analysed to indicate the usefulness of the test.

Chapter 3: Results

3.1. DJ Validity

ICC and CV values are displayed in Table 1 for all DJ Metrics.

Metric	ICC (95% CI)	CV% (95% CI)
DJH	0.998 (0.974-0.999)	0.79 (0.65-0.93)
DJ FT	0.998 (0.977-1.000)	0.37 (0.30-0.43)
DJ CT	1.00 (0.997-1.000)	0.54 (0.40-0.69)
DJ RSI	0.997 (0.983-0.999)	1.34 (1.07-1.62)

Table 1. Concurrent Validation of Optojump on DJ Metrics in Reference to Force Plates

Figure 1 displays the Optojump DJH T1, Force plate DJH T1, Optojump DJH T2, Force plate DJH T2. Mean \pm SD values were 24.6 cm \pm 4.7, 24.8 cm \pm 4.7, 24.5 cm \pm 4.2 and 24.6 cm \pm 4.2, respectively.

Figure 1. Descriptive Data of DJ Jump Height Measured Concurrently By The Optojump And Force Plates During Test Session 1 And 2.

The Bland-Altman analysis comparing Optojump and Force plate DJH demonstrated a systematic bias of -0.24 cm (95% CI, -0.17 to -0.32), accompanied by upper and lower limits of agreement (LoA)

of 0.12 cm (95% CI, 0.25 to -0.01) and -0.60 cm (95% CI, -0.47 to -0.73), respectively. Refer to Figure 2 for a visual representation.

Figure 2. Bland-Altman Plot of Optojump vs Force Plates DJ Jump Height

In Figure 3, the data for Optojump DJ FT T1, Force plate DJ FT T1, Optojump DJ FT T2, and Force plate DJ FT T2 is presented, with corresponding Mean \pm SD values of 0.446 s \pm 0.044, 0.448 s \pm 0.044, 0.445 s \pm 0.040, and 0.446 s \pm 0.040, respectively.

Figure 3. Descriptive Data Of DJ Flight Time Measured Concurrently By The Optojump And Force Plates During Test Session 1 And 2.

The Bland-Altman analysis conducted on Optojump and Force plate DJ FT revealed a systematic bias of -0.002 s (95% CI, -0.001 to -0.003), along with upper and lower LoA of 0.001 s (95% CI, 0.002 to 0.000) and -0.005 s (95% CI, -0.004 to -0.006), as depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Bland-Altman Plot of Optojump vs Force Plates DJ Flight Time

In Figure 5, the data for Optojump DJCT T1, Force plate DJCT T1, Optojump DJCT T2, and Force plate DJCT T2 is presented, with Mean values \pm SD of 0.296 s \pm 0.089, 0.294 s \pm 0.089, 0.251 s \pm 0.047, and 0.249 s \pm 0.047, respectively.

Figure 5. Descriptive Data of DJ Contact Time Measured Concurrently By The Optojump And Force Plates During Test Session 1 And 2

The Bland-Altman analysis comparing Optojump and Force plate DJ CT indicated a systematic bias of 0.0019 s (95% CI, 0.0025 to 0.0012) with upper and lower LoA of 0.0053 s (95% CI, 0.0065 to 0.0041) and -0.0015 s (95% CI, -0.0003 to -0.0027), as illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Descriptive Data of DJ Contact Time Measured Concurrently By The Optojump And Force Plates During Test Session 1 And 2

Figure 7 showcases data for Optojump DJ RSI T1, Force plate DJ RSI T1, Optojump DJ RSI T2, and Force plate DJ RSI T2, with Mean values \pm SD of 0.89 ± 0.26 , 0.90 ± 0.26 , 0.99 ± 0.18 , and 1.01 ± 0.18 , respectively.

Figure 7. Descriptive Data of DJ Contact Time Measured Concurrently By The Optojump And Force Plates During Test Session 1 And 2

Bland-Altman analysis of Optojump and Force plate DJ RSI revealed a systematic bias of -0.014 (95% CI, -0.008 and -0.020) with upper and lower LoA of 0.015 (95% CI, 0.025 and 0.004) and -0.043 (95% CI, -0.033 and -0.053), see figure 8.

Figure 8. Descriptive Data of DJ Contact Time Measured Concurrently By The Optojump And Force Plates During Test Session 1 And 2

3.2. CMJ Validity

ICC and CV values are displayed in Table 2 for all CMJ Metrics.

Metric	ICC (95% CI)	CV% (95% CI)
CMJH	0.997 (0.995-0.999)	0.54 (0.39-0.69)
CMJ FT	0.997 (0.982-0.999)	0.27 (0.19-0.34)

Table 2. Concurrent Validation of Optojump on CMJ Metrics in Reference to Force plate

Figure 9 displays the Optojump CMJH T1, Force plate CMJH T1, Optojump CMJH T2, Force plate CMJH T2. Mean \pm SD values were 27.7 cm \pm 3.6, 27.9 cm \pm 3.6, 27.4 cm \pm 3.9 and 27.6 cm \pm 3.9, respectively.

Figure 9. Descriptive Data of CMJ Jump Height Measured Concurrently By The Optojump And Force Plates During Test Session 1 And 2.

The Bland-Altman analysis, comparing Optojump and Force plate CMJH, unveiled a systematic bias of -0.185 cm (95% CI, -0.104 to -0.265), with upper and lower LoA of 0.206 cm (95% CI, 0.346 to 0.067) and -0.575 cm (95% CI, -0.436 to -0.715), as illustrated in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Bland-Altman Plot of Optojump vs Force Plates CMJ Jump Height

Figure 11 displays the Optojump CMJ FT T1, Force plate CMJ FT T1, Optojump CMJ FT T2, Force plate CMJ FT T2. Mean \pm SD values were 0.474 s \pm 0.031, 0.476 s \pm 0.031, 0.472 s \pm 0.034, 0.473 s \pm 0.034, respectively.

Figure 11. Descriptive Data Of CMJ Flight Time Measured Concurrently By The Optojump And Force Plates During Test Session 1 And 2

Bland-Altman analysis of Optojump and Force plate CMJ FT revealed a systematic bias of -0.002 s (95% CI, -0.001 and -0.002) with upper and lower LoA of 0.001 s (95% CI, 0.003 and 0.000) and -0.005 s (95% CI, -0.004 and -0.006), see figure 12.

Figure 12. Bland-Altman Plot of Optojump vs Force Plates CMJ Flight Time

3.3. DJ Test-Retest Reliability

Table 3 presents the test-retest reliability of Optojump DJ parameters. The CV% for Optojump JH, FT, CT, and RSI were 6.7%, 3.4%, 12.8%, and 13.5%, respectively. The CV, presented in unit form, for Optojump JH, FT, CT, and RSI were 1.6 cm, 0.015 s, 0.035 s and 0.13, respectively. The SWC values, for Optojump JH, FT, CT, and RSI were 0.82 cm, 0.008 s, 0.013 s and 0.04, respectively. Additionally, the ICC values, along with their 95% upper and lower CI, for the same parameters, were as follows: 0.72 (95% CI, 0.87 to 0.47), 0.75 (95% CI, 0.88 to 0.52), 0.61 (95% CI, 0.80 to 0.30), and 0.68 (95% CI, 0.84 to 0.40).

Jump Parameters	CV % (95 % CI)	CV	SWC	ICC (95 % CI)
Optojump DJH	6.7 (4.0-9.4)	1.64	0.82	0.72 (0.47-0.87)
Optojump DJ FT	3.4 (2.0-4.7)	0.015	0.008	0.75 (0.52-0.88)
Optojump DJ CT	12.8 (8.6-17.1)	0.035	0.013	0.61 (0.30-0.80)
Optojump DJ RSI	13.5 (9.2-17.8)	0.13	0.04	0.68 (0.40-0.84)

Table 3. DJ CV% with 95% Upper and Lower CI, CV, SWC and ICC 95% Upper and Lower CI

3.4. CMJ Test-Retest Reliability

Table 4 displays the test-retest reliability of the Optojump CMJ parameters. CV% for Optojump JH and Optojump FT were 2.8% and 1.4%. CV, presented as a unit, for Optojump JH and Optojump FT were 0.760 cm and 0.007 s. SWC values for Optojump JH and Optojump FT were 0.727 cm and 0.006 s. ICC with 95% upper and lower CI for the Optojump jump height and Optojump flight time were 0.89 (95% CI, 0.95 and 0.77), 0.89 (95% CI, 0.95 and 0.77).

Jump Parameters	CV % (95 % CI)	CV	SWC	ICC (95 % CI)
Optojump CMJH (cm)	2.8 (1.9-3.6)	0.760	0.727	0.89 (0.77-0.95)
Optojump CMJ FT (s)	1.4 (1.0-1.8)	0.007	0.006	0.89 (0.77-0.95)

Table 4. CMJ CV% with 95% Upper and Lower CI, CV, SWC and ICC 95% Upper and Lower CI

Chapter 4: Discussion

The purpose of this study was to investigate the validity and test-retest reliability of the metrics collected by the Optojump compared to force plates during the CMJ and DJ within female football players. The current findings indicated that there was strong validity and high level of agreement between the Optojump and force plates, however there was a small but consistent systematic bias present in all DJ and CMJ metrics. With the exception of DJ CT, the Optojump consistently underestimated jump metrics compared to the force plates. The Optojump device exhibited moderate test-retest reliability for DJH (ICC=0.72 (0.47 – 0.87)), DJ CT (ICC=0.61 (0.30-0.80)), and DJ RSI (ICC=0.68 (0.40-0.84)), whereas DJ FT demonstrated good test-retest reliability (ICC=0.75 (0.52-0.88)). The CV% values for DJ CT and DJ RSI did not meet the criteria for excellent reliability (CV < 10%) although DJH and DJ FT fulfilled the classification criteria for excellent reliability (6.7% and 3.4%, respectively). The SWC value was consistently smaller than the CV (Unit) for DJH (0.82, 1.64), DJ FT (0.008, 0.015), DJ CT (0.013, 0.035), and DJ RSI (0.04, 0.13), indicating that the CV (Unit) is a more reliable statistic for identifying usefulness and meaningful change in these tests. The Optojump device provided good test-retest reliability for CMJH (ICC=0.89 (0.77-0.95)) and CMJ FT (ICC=0.89 (0.77-0.95)) with CV% values being defined as excellent (2.8% and 1.4%). Similar to DJ metrics, the SWC values were consistently smaller than CV (unit) for CMJH (0.727, 0.760) and CMJ FT (0.006, 0.007) indicating the CV (Unit) is a better statistic to utilize when identifying usefulness and meaningful change in a test.

In this study, Bland-Altman plots and ICC values were employed to evaluate the level of agreement and subsequently the validity of the Optojump for all DJ and CMJ metrics. The findings suggest that systematic bias was present between measurement devices. Although there was excellent ICC and CV values between devices for all DJ (ICC > 0.99, CV < 1.35%) and CMJ (ICC > 0.99, CV < 0.55%) metrics, a small but consistent underestimation of DJH (-0.24 cm, 95% CI=-0.17 to -0.32) DJ FT (-0.002 s, 95% CI=-0.001 to -0.003), and DJ RSI (-0.014, 95% CI=-0.008 and -0.020) was evident for the Optojump device in comparison to the corresponding measurements obtained from the force plates. DJ CT was the only metric deviating from this trend, as the Optojump consistently demonstrated a small overestimation in comparison to the results obtained from the force plates (0.0019 s, 95% CI= 0.0025 to 0.0012). Similar findings were evident when examining the CMJ variables. An underestimation of CMJH (-0.185 cm, 95% CI=-0.104 to -0.265) and CMJ FT (-0.002 s, 95% CI=-0.001 and -0.002) was evident on the Optojump device in comparison to measurements from the force plates.

There is limited research investigating the validity of the Optojump at assessing DJ metrics compared to the force plates. Nevertheless, the results of this study align with research conducted by Healy et al. (2016), which also examined the concurrent validity of the Optojump device in comparison to force plates. Accordingly, Healy et al. (2016) reported near perfect ICC values ($ICC > 0.9$) for all DJ metrics but noted a consistent underestimation by the Optojump for DJ FT and DJ RSI, with a concurrent overestimation by the Optojump for DJ CT as compared to the force plates. In the study conducted by Healy et al. (2016) systematic bias was present as demonstrated by a mean difference \pm 95% LoA of $-0.004 \text{ s} \pm 0.002$ in DJ FT, $0.004 \text{ s} \pm 0.002$ in DJ CT, and -0.05 ± 0.04 in DJ RSI when comparing the measurements acquired from the Optojump and force plates. In the current study, the systematic bias was notably smaller, with mean differences of -0.002 s (95% CI, -0.001 to -0.003) for DJ FT, 0.0019 s (95% CI, 0.0025 to 0.0012) for DJ CT, and a 0.014 (95% CI, -0.008 and -0.020) for DJ RSI. Additionally, differing from present study's findings Healy et al. (2016) reported proportional bias present between the Optojump and force plates during measures of DJ CT, FT and RSI indicating that the error between the devices generally increases as the magnitude of the measure increases. The participants recruited in the study might have influenced the presence of proportional bias. Notably, Healy et al. (2016) recruited male participants from diverse sporting backgrounds, while the present study exclusively enrolled female football players. Given that the discrepancies between the devices generally grew with the magnitude of the measurements, it is reasonable to speculate that proportional bias was not discernible in the female participants of the current study, primarily because their results did not exhibit the same magnitude as those of the male participants in Healy et al.'s (2016) study. This reinforces the underpinning rationale for the current research, emphasising the necessity for the incorporation of female football players into validation and test-retest reliability studies of the Optojump.

The magnitude of differences between males and females jump performance has been well-documented. Research by Suchomel et al. (2015) serves as a notable example, highlighting the significant disparities in CMJH between males and females, with reported differences reaching up to 37.3%. Similarly, McMahon et al. (2017) found males to exhibit a 24% higher jump than their female counterparts, a trend which is consistently echoed in the findings of other studies (Laffaye, Wagner and Tomblason, 2014; Rice et al., 2017). The observed difference in jump performance between males and females is attributed to the higher percentage of muscle mass in males compared to females (Beckham et al., 2019; Hoeger et al., 1990; Suchomel et al., 2015). Although both males and females undergo muscle development at a similar rate, males develop larger muscle mass in comparison to their female counterparts, accompanied by a higher proportion of fast-twitch muscle fibres (Laubach, 1976; Decker et al., 2003). This greater muscle mass, coupled with a greater quantity

of fast-twitch muscle fibres, allows males to achieve higher levels of strength and power production than females. Consequently, contributing to their vastly greater jump performance. Findings from McMahon, Rej and Comfort. (2017) revealed the greater performance by males during the CMJ is a result of their application of a larger concentric impulse. This, in turn, leads to greater velocity throughout most of the concentric phase and at take-off. Male's ability to generate a larger concentric impulse and achieve higher velocity was due to their larger COM displacement during the unweighting/eccentric phase of the jump. Consequently, this allowed them to attain a greater COM displacement during the concentric phase of the jump, all while maintaining a similar movement time compared to women. The Optojump's underestimation of DJ RSI observed in the present study and that by Healy et al. (2016) is to be expected as the underlying metrics used in the calculation of this displayed discrepancies from the force plates. The Optojump's underestimation of DJ FT and overestimation of DJ CT can be explained by its physical design. Specifically, the placement of the transmitting and receiving units 0.003 meters above the floor differs from the configuration of the Force plate used in the current study, which was embedded in the floor. This design incongruity led to a disparity in the positions of the platform's surface and the photoelectric cells of the Optojump. Consequently, this divergence caused an early detection of CT and a delayed detection of FT when compared to the measures obtained from the force plates. The variances in configuration between the two measurement devices consequently resulted in the drop height from the 30cm bench being received as 29.7 cm by the Optojump. In accordance with Newton's laws of motion and free falling, and assuming all participants adhered to the pre-established protocol, it would take 0.2473s to drop from a 30cm box, whereas only 0.2461s to drop from a 29.7 cm box. This deviation in drop height velocity provides justification as to why these over and underestimations were found.

The outcomes of the present study agree with those of a study conducted by Montalvo et al. (2021) with the exception of the analysis of the DJH metric. Both studies found there to be very high ICC values (ICC=0.94 (0.92–0.96) and low CV values (CV=7.11% (5.38–8.49)) between measuring devices for DJH. However, in the study by Montalvo et al. (2021) the Optojump device demonstrated an overestimation of DJH (27.09 cm \pm 8.35 vs 25.79 cm \pm 8.39) and an underestimation of DJ RSI (0.71 \pm 0.40 vs 1.13 \pm 0.50) compared to the force plates. In contrast, in the present study, there was an underestimation of DJH (24.6 cm \pm 4.7 vs 24.8 cm \pm 4.7) and DJ RSI (0.89 \pm 0.26 vs 0.90 \pm 0.26). The substantial variation between devices for DJ RSI within their study compared to the lower variation in the present study could be attributed to the possible utilization of different equations for calculating DJ RSI between devices. It's worth noting that Montalvo et al. (2021) did not explicitly specify the equation they employed for calculating Force plate DJ RSI in their research. Optojump's formula for calculating RSI is $RSI = JH/CT/100$, this identical formula was applied in the present study when

determining DJ RSI on the force plates. However, it is plausible that a differing formula, such as $RSI=FT/CT$, may have been utilised in the calculation of RSI on the force plates within Montalvo et al.'s (2021) study. Such formula variation can indeed yield different results between the two measurement devices. Regardless of this, the authors concluded that the Optojump showed excellent validity when assessing DJH (ICC=0.94, CV=7.11%) with no systematic or proportional bias. Although, the Optojump was less valid when measuring DJ RSI as evidenced by CV values significantly surpassing the designated $CV<10\%$ threshold and ICC values falling within the "good" classification (ICC=0.89, CV=37.69%). Furthermore, in a disagreement from the outcomes of the current study, proportional bias was evident in the DJ RSI metric when comparing the two measurement devices. Notably, this observation bears resemblance to the findings of Healy et al. (2016). Interestingly, the authors did not report findings on DJ CT so comparisons could not be made with the present study's findings. These observations may not have been addressed by the authors, given that their primary focus was on the DJ RSI metric. Nonetheless, in light of the significant CV% reported and the identified presence of systematic and proportional bias within DJ RSI, it could have been advantageous to also report the validity of Optojump's DJ CT metric. DJ CT is an integral component in the calculation of DJ RSI. Inclusion of this additional metric would have facilitated a more comprehensive analysis of the Optojump, akin to the approach taken in both the present study and the research conducted by Healy et al. (2016).

The current study aligns with Glatthorn et al. (2011) on the Optojump validity for assessing CMJ metrics. Glatthorn et al. (2011) found an underestimation of 1 cm for the Optojump compared to the force plates measurements, indicating systematic bias. They also observed increasing differences between measurement devices with higher CMJ heights, suggesting proportional bias. The authors concluded that the 1 cm underestimation present between the Optojump and Force plate measurements was marginal coupled with high ICC values (ICC=0.998), therefore proposing the Optojump as a valid tool of CMJH. Although they do, however, caution against potential inaccuracies when using the Optojump for CMJH assessments interchangeable with the force plates as the systematic and proportional bias present between the measurement devices will cause different results between the devices. Given that one common application of the CMJ is to assess performance gains, utilising these devices interchangeably can lead to inconsistencies in data collection, potentially resulting in misinterpretation of the data. Glatthorn et al. (2011) recommend the inclusion of a correction equation if consistent use of one device is not feasible, enabling their interchangeable use with greater accuracy. In the current study, the systematic bias between the Optojump and force plates was -0.185 cm, significantly smaller than that of Glatthorn et al. (2011). While both studies show similarities, the considerable reduction in systematic bias in the present

study compared to Glatthorn et al. (2011) suggests that there may be a noteworthy difference in the findings. Additionally, in the current study, the high ICC (0.997, 95% CI: 0.995-0.999) and low CV (0.51%) values suggest an almost perfect correlation between the measurement devices. This alongside the minimal systematic bias and no evidence of proportional bias observed in the Bland-Altman plots reinforces the validity of the Optojump in assessing CMJH, with only minor differences compared to the force plates.

This study's findings align with prior research by Montalvo et al. (2021) who reported excellent validity for the Optojump (ICC=0.94, CV=7.95%) and observed a very small systematic bias but no proportional bias when comparing it to the force plate for measuring CMJH, although the findings in the present study demonstrate even higher validity than those reported by Montalvo et al. (2021). This is evident in the superior ICC (0.997, 95% CI: 0.995-0.999) and lower CV (0.51%) values, as well as the smaller degree of systematic bias present between measurement devices (-0.185 cm versus 1.78 cm). Interestingly, in contrast with the present study Montalvo et al. (2021) reported the systematic bias to be an overestimation of CMJH on the Optojump compared to force plates, whereas in the current study the Optojump system consistently underestimated CMJH. While one potential explanation could be attributed to the device's physical design, the contradictory findings from Montalvo et al. (2021) indicate that there may be alternative factors contributing to this discrepancy. Further research in this area is essential to uncover the underlying reasons for the observed differences and establish a clearer understanding. Of note, CMJ FT was not directly reported in the study by Montalvo et al. (2021) therefore not allowing direct comparison between the validity of the measurement devices for this metric. Examining whether the overestimation of CMJH observed in the study by Montalvo et al. (2021) extends to the CMJ FT would have been valuable. This consideration is especially notable the current study indicated an underestimation in both CMJH and CMJ FT, aligning with previous research findings (Castagna et al., 2013; Healy et al., 2016). Although this finding is to be expected given the Optojump utilises FT to calculate JH. Notably, the work done by Montalvo et al. (2021) incorporated both female volleyball players and physically active male participants. Given the lack of inclusion of female athletes in much of the current research, the significance of this study lies in demonstrating the validity of the Optojump within an under-researched population. However, the grouping of both female and male participants results, instead of exclusively females, along with the inclusion of only female volleyball players, indicates the need for dedicated research focussing exclusively on females, in particular female athletes in different sporting disciplines, to further explore and identify the Optojump's validity within this population. This reiterates the rationale for the present study in which only female football players

were recruited to establish the validity of the Optojump compared to the force plates during the CMJ.

The research conducted by Castagna et al. (2013) drew a few similarities to that of the current study. Castagna et al. (2013) reported the Optojump to record the presence of systematic bias as demonstrated by lower (1.27%) CMJ FT values when compared to the force plates. Although to a smaller magnitude this was similar to findings present in the current study (0.42%). Additionally, Castagna et al. (2013) reported a nearly perfect association ($r=0.99$; 95% CI 0.098–0.99; $p < 0.0001$) between the measurement devices assessment of CMJ FT, therefore providing strong support for the concurrent validity of the Optojump in detecting CMJ FT. Similarly, in the present study, concurrent validity was assessed by excellent ICC values (0.997, 95% CI: 0.995-0.999) and a low CV of 0.51%. Consistent with earlier research, the observed underestimation in CMJ FT measures could be attributed to the physical design of the Optojump, specifically variations in device positioning, detection threshold and the consistency of underlying surfaces (Glatthorn et al., 2011; Healy et al., 2016). Glatthorn et al. (2011) explained the variations between measurement devices could be attributed to several factors including the non-horizontal direction of the optojump rays, the emitting-receiving angle which may result in the measurement of prolonged pushing times (i.e., shorted flight times) during ankle extension when the feet are no longer in contact with the force plate but still fall within the field of the photoelectric cells, and finally the varying sensitivity of light signals from the Optojump in comparison to the vertical reaction force signals on the force plates. Similar findings were replicated in a study conducted by Słomka et al. (2017). The authors reported the Optojump to have a nearly perfect association with the force plates ($r=0.99$), indicating strong concurrent validity. The study revealed insignificant differences in CMJH measured simultaneously by both the Optojump and force plates, with the Optojump showing a slight underestimation of CMJH. The similarities between the findings of Słomka et al. (2017) and the present study indicate a high level of agreement between the Optojump and force plates when assessing CMJ metrics. Although a small amount of systematic bias was present between devices, the lack of significance in this variance reinforces the overall validity of the Optojump in assessing CMJ metrics.

In the current study, the test-retest reliability of the Optojump at assessing DJ metrics in comparison to force plates provided mixed results. Previous literature has investigated the test-retest reliability of the Optojump specifically for DJH and DJ RSI. However, there is limited research on the test-retest reliability of Optojump encompassing all DJ metrics measured by the device. This gap in the research becomes increasingly limited when seeking a participant pool that includes female athletes. This reiterates the significance of the present research, taking measures to address this gap in the literature by providing valuable data on the Optojump's validity and test-retest reliability within the

female football population. The findings from the current study were partially in agreement with work done by Montalvo et al. (2021). Montalvo et al. (2021) examined the test-retest reliability of the Optojump in terms of both relative (ICC) and absolute (CV) measures. The study revealed the Optojump to have excellent relative reliability in assessing DJH as highlighted through excellent ICC values (0.94 (0.90–0.97)). However, the CV values for Optojump DJH failed to meet the criteria for excellent absolute reliability (CV=12.04 (8.59–15.48)). Within the present study the findings demonstrated moderate test-retest relative reliability (ICC=0.72 (0.47-0.87) and CV values met the criteria for excellent classification (CV=6.7%). Therefore, it is evident similarities are present in the establishment of test-retest reliability, yet a disparity in the strength of the relative test-retest relationship. Additionally, the current study achieved excellent absolute reliability, a distinction from the findings of Montalvo et al. (2021). Montalvo et al. (2021) reported the Optojump to have excellent test-retest relative reliability (ICC=0.96 (0.93–0.97)) for DJ RSI. However, the device again did not satisfy the criteria for excellent absolute reliability (CV=19.9%, 95% CI: 15.22–24.58). This echoes the findings of the current study, in which the Optojump displayed moderate test-retest relative reliability (ICC=0.68, 95% CI: 0.40-0.84) and did not meet the criteria for excellent absolute reliability (CV=13.5%). One possible explanation for the results in the present study could be attributed to participants familiarity with the jump test utilised. Despite conducting familiarisation sessions, it is plausible that variations in participants performance may have occurred due to improvements in the technique employed for the jump. Although DJ FT was not specifically reported, it is reasonable to assume that similar results would have been observed in this metric, given that the Optojump utilises FT in calculating JH. Additionally, DJ CT was not reported by Montalvo et al. (2021), considering this metrics involvement in the calculation of RSI inclusion of DJ CT data would have been worthy for a comprehensive assessment of the Optojump's reliability. Condello et al. (2020) investigated the reliability of the Optojump at assessing CT during both lateral jumping and change of direction tasks. Their findings indicated that the Optojump overestimated contact time during these tasks, similar to what was seen in the present study. In their study, the Optojump exhibited moderate-good relative reliability for CT for all jump modalities (ICC=0.69-0.89). However, it failed to meet the criteria for excellent absolute reliability for all jump modality metrics (CV>10%). Moderate test-retest relative reliability (ICC=0.61) and poor absolute reliability (CV=12.8%) were also reported in the present study drawing similarities with this research. The current study also evidenced a small degree of systematic bias of CT on the Optojump in comparison to force plates, as demonstrated by overestimations by the Optojump. Regardless of the fact Condello et al. (2020) used a different jumping modality, it appears the reliability of the Optojump's measure of CT follows a similar trend. It is possible the low ICC values and high CV% values occur due to the complexity of

the DJ movement. Alternatively, differences in participants motivation to jump on different testing sessions could contribute to these results. Despite organising familiarisation sessions and providing motivation to participants during testing, variations in intrinsic motivation on different days might have influenced the findings in the present study. Additionally, biological fluctuations may contribute to the poor reliability reported in both the present study and that by Condello et al. (2020). Condello et al. (2020) recruited both male and female participants in their study, potentially accounting for the differences in findings. The inclusion of female basketball players in this research is beneficial as it demonstrates the reliability of the Optojump at assessing CT within this under-researched participation group. However, although a combination of male and female participants was utilised, the authors did not provide the specific numbers for each gender. Including this detail would have offered insight into the proportion of females included in the study and whether this was sufficient enough to generalize the research findings to the female basketball player population.

The findings in the present study indicate that the Optojump provided good test-retest reliability within female football players when measuring CMJH (ICC=0.89 (0.77-0.95), CV=2.8%) and CMJ FT (ICC=0.89 (0.77-0.95), CV=1.4%). While no research has been conducted in the same population, the current study's findings align with previous research conducted in different disciplines (Cormack et al., 2008; Glatthorn et al., 2011; Attia et al., 2017; Słomka et al., 2017; Montalvo et al., 2021). Montalvo et al. (2021) found the Optojump to have excellent test-retest reliability for the CMJH (ICC=0.98 (0.97–0.99), CV=8.14% (6.14–10.22)) among male and female participants with experience in plyometric training. Although no specific analyses was completed on CMJ FT, considering the Optojump utilises FT to calculate JH it would be expected that CMJ FT showed excellent test-retest reliability as was seen in the present study. Glatthorn et al. (2011) found the Optojump to have excellent test-retest reliability (ICC=0.989 (0.973-0.996), CV=2.2%) for CMJH within physically active male participants. Similarly, Cormack et al. (2008) found the Optojump to have excellent test-retest reliability for CMJH and CMJ FT (CV=5.0% and 3.3%, respectively) within male Australian League Football players. Although the small number of participants (n=15) used within the study warrants caution when interpreting results. These findings were replicated by Słomka et al. (2017) who reported excellent test-retest reliability (ICC=0.98 (0.958–0.991), CV=0.20%) within physically active males and volleyball players. Considering the practicality of the Optojump in comparison to the force plates as well as the cost-effectiveness of the device, the findings from this study are of practical importance as they suggest that Optojump provides a reliable measure of CMJ between devices within female football players, allowing for it to be used as an alternative to the force plates.

In the present study, SWC and CV (Unit) were calculated to assess the usefulness of the test and to determine whether a meaningful change in performance was present. Calculating the SWC helps

practitioners confirm that any observed changes between testing sessions are due to actual performance improvements rather than typical test variation (Spencer et al., 2006; Paton and Hopkins., 2005). The findings revealed that the SWC for DJ metrics was consistently lower than the CV (Unit) for DJH (0.82 cm, 1.64 cm), DJ FT (0.008 s, 0.015 s), DJ CT (0.013 s, 0.035 s), and DJ RSI (0.04, 0.13), respectively. Aswell as for CMJH (0.727 cm, 0.760 cm) and CMJ FT (0.006 s, 0.007 s), respectively. Conflicting findings were reported by Rago et al. (2018) in which the SWC was greater than the Standard Error of measurement (SEM) for CMJH (0.015 cm, 0.010 cm) and CMJ FT (0.013 s, 0.008 s), respectively. Regardless, the findings from the present study still suggest that the variation exhibited by the Optojump between tests exceeds what would be considered a meaningful change in performance. Therefore, in this context, the CV (Unit) may be a more appropriate statistic for interpreting results, helping to avoid misinterpretation of the data.

4.1. Limitations and Future Research

This study is not without its limitations. The current study exclusively recruited from 1 team within the top league of women's football in Scotland and selected the best jump trial from a total of 3 for analysis, therefore limiting the participant size and subsequently the number of data points to 26. The inclusion of multiple teams, as well as using all 3 jump trials in the analysis, may have provided a more comprehensive interpretation of the Optojump in comparison to force plates, although the approach of taking the best jump trial of 3 was used to keep consistency with much of the current literature. Additionally, although the jumps employed in the study are commonly used, it is acknowledged that there are multiple other tests available for measures of lower-body power and RSI. Conducting an in-depth analysis of all commonly used performance tests could be beneficial to indicate which performance test the Optojump provides the most valid and reliable results for within the chosen population group. Furthermore, it is important to note that the method for JH calculation on the force plates used within the present study was the FT method. It is acknowledged that JH can be calculated on the force plates using different and perhaps more accurate methods such as take-off velocity, impulse-momentum, and take-off velocity + displacement of the centre of mass (COM) (Xu et al., 2023), however the choice was made to maintain consistency with the Optojump, which utilises the FT method to calculate JH. The FT Method has been reported to carry the potential for introducing error, particularly if the participant does not land with the correct body position. For instance, increased hip, knee, or plantar flexion upon landing may register as increased FT and, consequently, increased JH (Vanreenterghem, De Clercq and Van Cleven, 2001). The present study did attempt to address this potential source of error by providing clear instructions to participants. These were to consistently land with fully extended hips and knees, and ankles plantarflexed until ground contact. Following contact, participants were permitted to use hip, knee, and ankle flexion to

attenuate forces and minimise the risk of injury. If these guidelines were not adhered to then the trial would have been removed and the participant was required to repeat it. Whilst the participants in the current study had experience performing the jumps, it must be recognised that individual mechanics could have varied and potentially introduced errors to the jump metrics. Future research should investigate the validity and test-retest reliability of the Optojump compared to force plates within female football players using other JH calculating methods such as impulse-momentum. This approach may provide a more accurate calculation of JH on the force plates, allowing for a more valid and reliable comparison against Optojump outputs and enhancing the overall evaluation. Finally, the statistical approach for interpreting the validity and test-retest reliability of the Optojump compared of force plates differs significantly across existing literature. The approach taken within the present study was considered adequate for reporting meaningful data, potential inclusion of ordinary least product regressions as used within Montalvo et al. (2021) may have been beneficial and allowed for comparisons between studies however the current study utilised statistical methods similar to those in previous research and offered findings for an under-researched participant pool.

4.2. Practical Applications

The findings from the present study have significant implications for practitioners working in football. The results suggest that the Optojump device is a viable alternative for assessing both CMJ and DJ metrics when a force plate is unavailable, as both metrics demonstrated good validity. However, the systematic bias observed between Optojump and force plate measurements could lead to inaccuracies if practitioners switch between the devices. It is important for practitioners to note that the Optojump demonstrated a tendency to overestimate CMJH, CMJ FT, DJH, DJ FT, and DJ RSI, while underestimating DJ CT. These minor discrepancies between devices highlight the importance of maintaining consistency in the measurement tools used. If the use of consistent measurement tools is not possible then a correction equation is required to be used. Future research is required to establish this.

The present findings suggest that the Optojump device is suitable for assessing CMJH and CMJ FT in a test-retest scenario, but it should not be used to evaluate DJ metrics across different time-points. Although DJH and DJ FT exhibited moderate to good test-retest reliability, as indicated by ICC and CV% values, the CV% values for DJ CT and DJ RSI suggest that these metrics are not reliable for test-retest scenarios. However, caution must be taken with this finding, as the reliability statistics for the DJ metrics may have been influenced by participants familiarisation with the jump technique. Although familiarisation sessions were conducted over a 4 week period, which included programming of the jumps into participants regular gym programmes, this study suggests a more

comprehensive familiarisation process may be necessary to ensure correct execution of the DJ technique across two separate time-points

Additionally, the findings of the present study indicate that for both CMJ and DJ metrics, the SWC is smaller than the CV (unit). Consequently, practitioners cannot confidently attribute the SWC to anything other than measurement variation. It is recommended that CV (Unit) be used to identify meaningful changes in performance when assessing these metrics, rather than relying on SWC.

Chapter 5: Conclusion

To the best of the authors knowledge this is the first study to investigate the validity and test-retest reliability of the Optojump compared to force plates at assessing CMJ and DJ metrics within female football players. The findings from the current study indicate that the Optojump may serve as a viable alternative to the force plates for measuring CMJH, CMJ FT, DJH and DJ FT but not DJ CT or DJ RSI. However, caution must be taken when interpreting these results as despite excellent ICC (ICC > 0.9) and very small CV values (CV < 2%) between devices, there was a presence of systematic bias reported in all CMJ and DJ metrics. Although to a very small degree, a trend of underestimations were found in in all DJ and CMJ metrics with the exception of DJ CT, with this being accredited to the physical design of the Optojump. Moderate to good test-retest reliability was found for DJH (ICC=0.72 (0.47 -0.87), CV=6.7%) and DJ FT (ICC=0.75 (0.52-0.88), CV=3.4%) but in DJ CT and consequently DJ RSI the CV values failed to meet the criteria for excellent reliability (CV > 10%) despite having moderate test-retest ICC values (ICC > 0.5 < 0.75). Thus, indicating the Optojump should not be used to assess DJ CT or DJ RSI within a test-retest setting. Good test-retest reliability was reported for both CMJH (ICC=0.89 (0.77-0.95), CV=2.8%) and CMJ FT (ICC=0.89 (0.77-0.95), CV=1.4%) therefore indicating the Optojump can be used to assess these variables in absence of a Force plate. SWC values for both DJ and CMJ metrics indicate the CV (Unit) should be used to identify meaningful change in performance rather than the SWC as SWC values were consistently smaller than the CV.

References

- Aagaard, P., Simonsen, E. B., Andersen, J. L., Magnusson, P. and Dyhre-Poulsen, P. (2002) Increased rate of force development and neural drive of human skeletal muscle following resistance training. Journal of applied physiology (Bethesda, Md. : 1985). [Online] Vol.93 (4), pp.1318–1326. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/12235031/> [Accessed 28 Aug 2023].
- Addie, C. D., Arnett, J. E., Neltner, T. J., Straughn, M. K., Greska, E. K., Cosio-Lima, L. and Brown, L. E. (2019) Effects of Drop Height on Drop Jump Performance. International Journal of Kinesiology and Sports Science. [Online] Vol.7 (4), pp.28–32. Available: <https://journals.aiac.org.au/index.php/IJKSS/article/view/5667> [Accessed 6 Dec 2023].
- Andersen, L. L. and Aagaard, P. (2006) Influence of maximal muscle strength and intrinsic muscle contractile properties on contractile rate of force development. European journal of applied physiology. [Online] Vol.96 (1), pp.46–52. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/16249918/> [Accessed 28 Aug 2023].
- Andersson, H., Raastad, T., Nilsson, J., Paulsen, G., Garthe, I. and Kadi, F. (2008) Neuromuscular fatigue and recovery in elite female soccer: Effects of active recovery. Medicine and Science in Sports and Exercise. [Online] Vol.40 (2), pp.372–380. Available: https://journals.lww.com/acsm-msse/Fulltext/2008/02000/Neuromuscular_Fatigue_and_Recovery_in_Elite_Female.24.aspx [Accessed 26 Jul 2022].
- Aragon-Vargas, L. F. (2000) Evaluation of Four Vertical Jump Tests: Methodology, Reliability, Validity, and Accuracy. Measurement in Physical Education and Exercise Science. [Online] Vol.4 (4), pp.215–228. Available: https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1207/S15327841MPPE0404_2 [Accessed 27 Nov 2023].
- Atkinson, G. and Nevill, A. M. (1998) Statistical methods for assessing measurement error (reliability) in variables relevant to sports medicine. Sports Medicine. [Online] Vol.26 (4), pp.217–238. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/13465624_Statistical_Methods_For_Assessing_Measurement_Error_Reliability_in_Variables_Relevant_to_Sports_Medicine [Accessed 30 Oct 2023].

- Attia, A., Dhahbi, W., Chaouachi, A., Padulo, J., Wong, D. P. and Chamari, K. (2017) Measurement errors when estimating the vertical jump height with flight time using photocell devices: the example of Optojump. Biology of Sport. [Online] Vol.34 (1), p.63. Available: /pmc/articles/PMC5377563/ [Accessed 10 Nov 2021].
- Barnes, C., Archer, D. T., Hogg, B., Bush, M. and Bradley, P. S. (2014) The evolution of physical and technical performance parameters in the English Premier League. International journal of sports medicine. [Online] Vol.35 (13), pp.1095–1100. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/25009969/> [Accessed 26 Jul 2022].
- Barr, M. J. and Nolte, V. W. (2011) Which measure of drop jump performance best predicts sprinting speed? Journal of strength and conditioning research. [Online] Vol.25 (7), pp.1976–1982. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/21701285/> [Accessed 30 Oct 2023].
- Beattie, K., Carson, B. P., Lyons, M. and Kenny, I. C. (2017) The Relationship Between Maximal Strength and Reactive Strength. International journal of sports physiology and performance. [Online] Vol.12 (4), pp.548–553. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27618527/> [Accessed 30 Oct 2023].
- Beckham, G. K., Suchomel, T. J., Sole, C. J., Bailey, C. A., Grazer, J. L., Kim, S. B., Talbot, K. B. and Stone, M. H. (2019) Influence of Sex and Maximum Strength on Reactive Strength Index-Modified. Journal of Sports Science & Medicine. [Online] Vol.18 (1), p.65. Available: /pmc/articles/PMC6370960/ [Accessed 22 Mar 2022].
- Bradley, P. S. and Vescovi, J. D. (2015) Velocity thresholds for women’s soccer matches: sex specificity dictates high-speed running and sprinting thresholds - Female Athletes in Motion (FAiM). International journal of sports physiology and performance. [Online] Vol.10 (1), pp.112–116. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/25203354/> [Accessed 23 Jun 2022].
- Brughelli, M., Cronin, J., Levin, G. and Chaouachi, A. (2008) Understanding Change of Direction Ability in Sport. Sports Medicine. Vol.38 (12), pp.1045–1063.
- Buchheit, M., Samozino, P., Glynn, J. A., Michael, B. S., Al Haddad, H., Mendez-Villanueva, A. and Morin, J. B. (2014) Mechanical determinants of acceleration and maximal sprinting speed in highly trained young soccer players. Journal of sports sciences. [Online] Vol.32 (20), pp.1906–1913. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/25356503/> [Accessed 10 May 2023].

- Castagna, C., Ganzetti, M., Ditroilo, M., Giovannelli, M., Rocchetti, A. and Manzi, V. (2013) Concurrent validity of vertical jump performance assessment systems. Journal of Strength and Conditioning Research. [Online] Vol.27 (3), pp.761–768. Available: https://journals.lww.com/nsca-jscr/Fulltext/2013/03000/Concurrent_Validity_of_Vertical_Jump_Performance.28.aspx [Accessed 20 Apr 2022].
- Castillo-Rodríguez, A., Fernández-García, J. C., Chinchilla-Minguet, J. L. and Carnero, E. Á. (2012) Relationship between muscular strength and sprints with changes of direction. Journal of strength and conditioning research. [Online] Vol.26 (3), pp.725–732. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/22289697/> [Accessed 2 Jul 2022].
- Cavagna, G. A., Saibene, F. P. and Margaria, R. (1965) EFFECT OF NEGATIVE WORK ON THE AMOUNT OF POSITIVE WORK PERFORMED BY AN ISOLATED MUSCLE. Journal of applied physiology. [Online] Vol.20 (1), pp.157–158. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/14257547/> [Accessed 23 Jun 2022].
- Chiu, L. Z. F. and Dæhlin, T. E. (2020a) Comparing Numerical Methods to Estimate Vertical Jump Height Using a Force Platform. Measurement in Physical Education and Exercise Science. [Online] Vol.24 (1), pp.25–32. Available: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/1091367X.2019.1650044> [Accessed 22 Nov 2023].
- Chiu, L. Z. F. and Dæhlin, T. E. (2020b) Comparing Numerical Methods to Estimate Vertical Jump Height Using a Force Platform. Measurement in Physical Education and Exercise Science. [Online] Vol.24 (1), pp.25–32. Available: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/1091367X.2019.1650044> [Accessed 27 Nov 2023].
- Claudino, J. G., Cronin, J., Mezêncio, B., McMaster, D. T., McGuigan, M., Tricoli, V., Amadio, A. C. and Serrão, J. C. (2017) The countermovement jump to monitor neuromuscular status: A meta-analysis. Journal of science and medicine in sport. [Online] Vol.20 (4), pp.397–402. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27663764/> [Accessed 27 Nov 2023].
- Colyer, S. L., Nagahara, R., Takai, Y. and Salo, A. I. T. (2018) How sprinters accelerate beyond the velocity plateau of soccer players: Waveform analysis of ground reaction forces. Scandinavian Journal of Medicine & Science in Sports. [Online] Vol.28 (12), pp.2527–2535.

Available: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1111/sms.13302> [Accessed 10 May 2023].

- Comfort, P., Jones, P. A., Thomas, C., Dos'Santos, T., McMahon, J. J. and Suchomel, T. J. (2022) Changes in Early and Maximal Isometric Force Production in Response to Moderate- and High-Load Strength and Power Training. Journal of strength and conditioning research. [Online] Vol.36 (3), pp.593–599. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32187146/> [Accessed 28 Aug 2023].
- Condello, G., Khemtong, C., Lee, Y. H., Chen, C. H., Mandorino, M., Santoro, E., Liu, C. and Tessitore, A. (2020) Validity and Reliability of a Photoelectric Cells System for the Evaluation of Change of Direction and Lateral Jumping Abilities in Collegiate Basketball Athletes. Journal of functional morphology and kinesiology. [Online] Vol.5 (3). Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33467270/> [Accessed 10 Nov 2021].
- Cormack, S. J., Newton, R. U., McGulgan, M. R. and Doyle, T. L. A. (2008) Reliability of Measures Obtained During Single and Repeated Countermovement Jumps. International Journal of Sports Physiology and Performance. [Online] Vol.3 (2), pp.131–144. Available: <https://journals.humankinetics.com/view/journals/ijsp/3/2/article-p131.xml> [Accessed 30 Oct 2023].
- Decker, M. J., Torry, M. R., Wyland, D. J., Sterett, W. I. and Steadman, J. R. (2003) Gender differences in lower extremity kinematics, kinetics and energy absorption during landing. Clinical biomechanics (Bristol, Avon). [Online] Vol.18 (7), pp.662–669. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/12880714/> [Accessed 4 Jul 2022].
- Dias, J. A., Pupo, J. D., Reis, D. C., Borges, L., Santos, S. G., Moro, A. R. P. and Borges, N. G. (2011) Validity of two methods for estimation of vertical jump height. Journal of strength and conditioning research. [Online] Vol.25 (7), pp.2034–2039. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/21701288/> [Accessed 27 Nov 2023].
- Emmonds, S., Nicholson, G., Begg, C., Jones, B. and Bissas, A. (2019) Importance of Physical Qualities for Speed and Change of Direction Ability in Elite Female Soccer Players. Journal of strength and conditioning research. [Online] Vol.33 (6), pp.1669–1677. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28723816/> [Accessed 10 May 2023].
- Faude, O., Koch, T. and Meyer, T. (2012) Straight sprinting is the most frequent action in goal situations in professional football. Journal of sports sciences. [Online] Vol.30 (7), pp.625–631. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/22394328/> [Accessed 10 May 2023].

- Furlong, L. A. M., Harrison, A. J. and Jensen, R. L. (2021) Measures of Strength and Jump Performance Can Predict 30-m Sprint Time in Rugby Union Players. Journal of strength and conditioning research. [Online] Vol.35 (9), pp.2579–2583. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31009436/> [Accessed 30 Oct 2023].
- Gathercole, R. J., Sporer, B. C., Stellingwerff, T. and Sleivert, G. G. (2015) Comparison of the Capacity of Different Jump and Sprint Field Tests to Detect Neuromuscular Fatigue. Journal of strength and conditioning research. [Online] Vol.29 (9), pp.2522–2531. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/26308829/> [Accessed 30 Nov 2021].
- Glatthorn, J. F., Gouge, S., Nussbaumer, S., Stauffacher, S., Impellizzeri, F. M. and Maffiuletti, N. A. (2011) Validity and reliability of optojump photoelectric cells for estimating vertical jump height. Journal of Strength and Conditioning Research. [Online] Vol.25 (2), pp.556–560. Available: https://journals.lww.com/nsca-jscr/Fulltext/2011/02000/Validity_and_Reliability_of_Optojump_Photoelectric.37.aspx [Accessed 2 Mar 2022].
- Goral, K. (2015) Examination of agility performances of soccer players according to their playing positions. The Sport Journal. [Online]. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/273575475_Examination_of_agility_performances_of_soccer_players_according_to_their_playing_positions [Accessed 10 May 2023].
- Hackett, D., Davies, T., Soomro, N. and Halaki, M. (2016) Olympic weightlifting training improves vertical jump height in sportspeople: a systematic review with meta-analysis. British journal of sports medicine. [Online] Vol.50 (14), pp.865–872. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/26626268/> [Accessed 27 Nov 2023].
- Haugen, T. A., Tønnessen, E. and Seiler, S. (2013) Anaerobic performance testing of professional soccer players 1995-2010. International journal of sports physiology and performance. [Online] Vol.8 (2), pp.148–156. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/22868347/> [Accessed 10 May 2023].
- Haynes, T., Bishop, C., Antrobus, M. and Brazier, J. (2019) The validity and reliability of the My Jump 2 app for measuring the reactive strength index and drop jump performance. Journal of Sports Medicine and Physical Fitness. pp.253–258.
- Healy, R., Kenny, I. C. and Harrison, A. J. (2016a) Assessing Reactive Strength Measures in Jumping and Hopping Using the Optojump™ System. Journal of Human Kinetics. [Online] Vol.54 (1), p.23. Available: [/pmc/articles/PMC5187958/](https://pmc/articles/PMC5187958/) [Accessed 26 Nov 2021].

- Healy, R., Kenny, I. C. and Harrison, A. J. (2016b) Assessing Reactive Strength Measures in Jumping and Hopping Using the Optojump™ System. Journal of human kinetics. [Online] Vol.54 (1), pp.23–32. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28031754/> [Accessed 10 Nov 2021].
- Healy, R., Kenny, I. C. and Harrison, A. J. (2018) Reactive Strength Index: A Poor Indicator of Reactive Strength? International journal of sports physiology and performance. [Online] Vol.13 (6), pp.802–809. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29182434/> [Accessed 28 Aug 2023].
- Höög, S. and Andersson, E. P. (2021) Sex and Age-Group Differences in Strength, Jump, Speed, Flexibility, and Endurance Performances of Swedish Elite Gymnasts Competing in TeamGym. Frontiers in sports and active living. [Online] Vol.3. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34056587/> [Accessed 6 Dec 2023].
- de Hoyo, M., Dylan Cohen, D., Sañudo, B., Carrasco, L., Álvarez-Mesa, A., José del Ojo, J., Domínguez-Cobo, S., Mañas, V. and Otero-Esquina, C. (2016) Influence of football match time-motion parameters on recovery time course of muscle damage and jump ability. Journal of Sports Sciences. [Online] Vol.34 (14), pp.1363–1370. Available: <https://www.tandfonline.com/action/journalInformation?journalCode=rjsp20> [Accessed 31 Jan 2022].
- Hughes, W., Healy, R., Lyons, M., Nevill, A., Higginbotham, C., Lane, A. and Beattie, K. (2023) The Effect of Different Strength Training Modalities on Sprint Performance in Female Team-Sport Athletes: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. Sports Medicine 2023 53:5. [Online] Vol.53 (5), pp.993–1015. Available: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s40279-023-01820-5> [Accessed 28 Aug 2023].
- Jarvis, P., Turner, A., Read, P. and Bishop, C. (2022) Reactive Strength Index and its Associations with Measures of Physical and Sports Performance: A Systematic Review with Meta-Analysis. Sports Medicine. [Online] Vol.52 (2), pp.301–330. Available: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s40279-021-01566-y> [Accessed 20 Apr 2022].
- Jones, B., Emmonds, S., Hind, K., Nicholson, G., Rutherford, Z. and Till, K. (2016) Physical Qualities of International Female Rugby League Players by Playing Position. Journal of strength and conditioning research. [Online] Vol.30 (5), pp.1333–1340. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/26439784/> [Accessed 16 Nov 2023].

- Jones, M. T., Jagim, A. R., Haff, G. G., Carr, P. J., Martin, J. and Oliver, J. M. (2016) Greater Strength Drives Difference in Power between Sexes in the Conventional Deadlift Exercise. Sports. [Online] Vol.4 (3). Available: </pmc/articles/PMC5968884/> [Accessed 10 May 2023].
- Keller, S., Koob, A., Corak, D., von Schöning, V. and Born, D. P. (2020) How to Improve Change-of-Direction Speed in Junior Team Sport Athletes-Horizontal, Vertical, Maximal, or Explosive Strength Training? Journal of strength and conditioning research. [Online] Vol.34 (2), pp.473–482. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30199451/> [Accessed 3 Jul 2022].
- Kibele, A. (1998) Possibilities and Limitations in the Biomechanical Analysis of Countermovement Jumps: A Methodological Study. Journal of Applied Biomechanics. [Online] Vol.14 (1), pp.105–117. Available: <https://journals.humankinetics.com/view/journals/jab/14/1/article-p105.xml> [Accessed 27 Nov 2023].
- Kobal, R., Freitas, T. T., Fíler, A., Requena, B., Barroso, R., Rossetti, M., Jorge, R. M., Carvalho, L., Pereira, L. A. and Loturco, I. (2021) Curve Sprint in Elite Female Soccer Players: Relationship with Linear Sprint and Jump Performance. International journal of environmental research and public health. [Online] Vol.18 (5), pp.1–10. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33652735/> [Accessed 9 May 2023].
- Komi, P. v. (2000) Stretch-shortening cycle: a powerful model to study normal and fatigued muscle. Journal of biomechanics. [Online] Vol.33 (10), pp.1197–1206. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/10899328/> [Accessed 24 Jun 2022].
- Koo, T. K. and Li, M. Y. (2016) A Guideline of Selecting and Reporting Intraclass Correlation Coefficients for Reliability Research. Journal of chiropractic medicine. [Online] Vol.15 (2), pp.155–163. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27330520/> [Accessed 7 Aug 2023].
- Kozinc, Ž. and Pleša, J. (2023) Discrepancy Among Different Methods for Vertical Jump Height Determination and Its Implications for Field-Based Testing: A Narrative Review. Measurement in Physical Education and Exercise Science. [Online] Vol.27 (3), pp.248–256. Available: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/1091367X.2022.2163398> [Accessed 27 Nov 2023].
- Laffaye, G., Wagner, P. P. and Tombleson, T. I. L. (2014) Countermovement jump height: gender and sport-specific differences in the force-time variables. Journal of strength and

- conditioning research. [Online] Vol.28 (4), pp.1096–1105. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/23838969/> [Accessed 3 Dec 2023].
- Laubach, L. L. (1976) Comparative muscular strength of men and women: a review of the literature. Aviation, Space, and Environmental Medicine. [Online] Vol.47 (5), pp.534–542. Available: <https://europepmc.org/article/med/1275845> [Accessed 4 Jul 2022].
- Linthorne, N. P. (2001) Analysis of standing vertical jumps using a force platform. American Journal of Physics. [Online] Vol.69 (11), pp.1198–1204. Available: [/aapt/ajp/article/69/11/1198/529369/Analysis-of-standing-vertical-jumps-using-a-force](https://aapt.ajp/article/69/11/1198/529369/Analysis-of-standing-vertical-jumps-using-a-force) [Accessed 27 Nov 2023].
- Lockie, R. G. (2014a) Contribution of leg power to multidirectional speed in field sport athletes Optimizing post-activation performance enhancement View project Heart Rate Responses during Simulated Fire Ground Scenarios among Full-Time Firefighters View project. [Online]. Available: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/269702046> [Accessed 2 Jul 2022].
- Lockie, R. G. (2014b) Contribution of leg power to multidirectional speed in field sport athletes. [Online]. Available: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/269702046> [Accessed 4 Jul 2022].
- Lockie, R. G., Dawes, J. J. and Jones, M. T. (2018) Relationships between Linear Speed and Lower-Body Power with Change-of-Direction Speed in National Collegiate Athletic Association Divisions I and II Women Soccer Athletes. Sports. [Online] Vol.6 (2). Available: [/pmc/articles/PMC6026790/](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32301681/) [Accessed 9 May 2023].
- Lombard, W., Starling, L., Wewege, L. and Lambert, M. (2021) Changes in countermovement jump performance and subjective readiness-to-train scores following a simulated soccer match. European journal of sport science. [Online] Vol.21 (5), pp.647–655. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32301681/> [Accessed 7 Feb 2022].
- Loturco, I., Kobal, R., Kitamura, K., Fernandes, V., Moura, N., Siqueira, F., Cal Abad, C. C. and Pereira, L. A. (2019) Predictive Factors of Elite Sprint Performance: Influences of Muscle Mechanical Properties and Functional Parameters. Journal of strength and conditioning research. [Online] Vol.33 (4), pp.974–986. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30913203/> [Accessed 30 Oct 2023].

- Maffiuletti, N. A., Aagaard, P., Blazevich, A. J., Folland, J., Tillin, N. and Duchateau, J. (2016) Rate of force development: physiological and methodological considerations. European journal of applied physiology. [Online] Vol.116 (6), pp.1091–1116. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/26941023/> [Accessed 28 Aug 2023].
- Mara, J. K., Thompson, K. G., Pumpa, K. L. and Morgan, S. (2017) The acceleration and deceleration profiles of elite female soccer players during competitive matches. Journal of Science and Medicine in Sport. Vol.20 (9), pp.867–872.
- Markovic, G. (2007) Does plyometric training improve vertical jump height? A meta-analytical review. British journal of sports medicine. [Online] Vol.41 (6), pp.349–355. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/17347316/> [Accessed 27 Nov 2023].
- Mccurdy, K. W., Walker, J. L., Langford, G. A., Kutz, M. R., Guerrero, J. M. and Mcmillan, J. (2010) The relationship between kinematic determinants of jump and sprint performance in division I women soccer players. Journal of strength and conditioning research. [Online] Vol.24 (12), pp.3200–3208. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/21068677/> [Accessed 16 Nov 2023].
- McMahon, J. J., Jones, P. A., Suchomel, T. J., Lake, J. and Comfort, P. (2018) Influence of the Reactive Strength Index Modified on Force– and Power–Time Curves. International Journal of Sports Physiology and Performance. [Online] Vol.13 (2), pp.220–227. Available: <https://journals.humankinetics.com/view/journals/ijsp/13/2/article-p220.xml> [Accessed 13 Mar 2023].
- McMahon, J. J., Murphy, S., Rej, S. J. E. and Comfort, P. (2017) Countermovement-Jump-Phase Characteristics of Senior and Academy Rugby League Players. International Journal of Sports Physiology and Performance. [Online] Vol.12 (6), pp.803–811. Available: <https://journals.humankinetics.com/view/journals/ijsp/12/6/article-p803.xml> [Accessed 13 Mar 2023].
- McMahon, J. J., Rej, S. J. E. and Comfort, P. (2017a) Sex Differences in Countermovement Jump Phase Characteristics. Sports (Basel, Switzerland). [Online] Vol.5 (1). Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29910368/> [Accessed 13 Mar 2023].
- McMahon, J. J., Rej, S. J. E. and Comfort, P. (2017b) Sex Differences in Countermovement Jump Phase Characteristics. Sports. [Online] Vol.5 (1). Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35969005/> [Accessed 3 Dec 2023].

- Mohr, M., Krstrup, P. and Bangsbo, J. (2005) Fatigue in soccer: a brief review. Journal of sports sciences. [Online] Vol.23 (6), pp.593–599. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/16195008/> [Accessed 26 Jul 2022].
- Moir, G. L. (2008) Three Different Methods of Calculating Vertical Jump Height from Force Platform Data in Men and Women. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10913670802349766>. [Online] Vol.12 (4), pp.207–218. Available: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/10913670802349766> [Accessed 27 Jul 2022].
- Montalvo, S. and Dorgo, S. (2019) The effect of different stretching protocols on vertical jump measures in college age gymnasts. The Journal of sports medicine and physical fitness. [Online] Vol.59 (12), pp.1956–1962. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31933341/> [Accessed 19 Apr 2022].
- Montalvo, S., Gonzalez, M. P., Dietze-Hermosa, M. S., Eggleston, J. D. and Dorgo, S. (2021a) Common Vertical Jump and Reactive Strength Index Measuring Devices: A Validity and Reliability Analysis. Journal of Strength and Conditioning Research. [Online] Vol.35 (5), pp.1234–1243. Available: https://journals.lww.com/nsca-jscr/Fulltext/2021/05000/Common_Vertical_Jump_and_Reactive_Strength_Index.10.aspx [Accessed 2 Mar 2022].
- Montalvo, S., Gonzalez, M. P., Dietze-Hermosa, M. S., Eggleston, J. D. and Dorgo, S. (2021b) Common Vertical Jump and Reactive Strength Index Measuring Devices: A Validity and Reliability Analysis. Journal of strength and conditioning research. [Online] Vol.35 (5), pp.1234–1243. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33629975/> [Accessed 10 Nov 2021].
- Morin, J. B., Edouard, P. and Samozino, P. (2011a) Technical ability of force application as a determinant factor of sprint performance. Medicine and science in sports and exercise. Vol.43 (9), pp.1680–1688.
- Morin, J. B., Edouard, P. and Samozino, P. (2011b) Technical ability of force application as a determinant factor of sprint performance. Medicine and science in sports and exercise. [Online] Vol.43 (9), pp.1680–1688. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/21364480/> [Accessed 27 Sep 2023].
- Mujika, I., Santisteban, J., Impellizzeri, F. M. and Castagna, C. (2009) Fitness determinants of success in men’s and women’s football. Journal of Sports Sciences. [Online] Vol.27 (2),

pp.107–114. Available:

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/23572994_Fitness_determinants_of_success_in_men's_and_women's_football [Accessed 10 May 2023].

Nicol, C., Avela, J. and Komi, P. v. (2006) The stretch-shortening cycle : a model to study naturally occurring neuromuscular fatigue. Sports medicine (Auckland, N.Z.). [Online] Vol.36 (11), pp.977–999. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/17052133/> [Accessed 23 Jun 2022].

Nimphius, S., McGuigan, M. R. and Newton, R. U. (2010) Relationship between strength, power, speed, and change of direction performance of female softball players. Journal of Strength and Conditioning Research. [Online] Vol.24 (4), pp.885–895. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/42345586_Relationship_Between_Strength_Power_Speed_and_Change_of_Direction_Performance_of_Female_Softball_Players [Accessed 27 Sep 2023].

Noffal, G. J. and Lynn, S. K. (2012) Biomechanics of power in sport. Strength and Conditioning Journal. [Online] Vol.34 (6), pp.20–24. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/271998602_Biomechanics_of_Power_in_Sport [Accessed 28 Aug 2023].

Northeast, J., Russell, M., Shearer, D., Cook, C. J. and Kilduff, L. P. (2019) Predictors of Linear and Multidirectional Acceleration in Elite Soccer Players. Journal of strength and conditioning research. [Online] Vol.33 (2), pp.514–522. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28301441/> [Accessed 4 Jul 2022].

Nygaard Falch, H., Guldteig Rædergård, H. and van den Tillaar, R. (2019) Effect of Different Physical Training Forms on Change of Direction Ability: a Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. Sports Medicine - Open 2019 5:1. [Online] Vol.5 (1), pp.1–37. Available: <https://sportsmedicine-open.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s40798-019-0223-y> [Accessed 19 Dec 2023].

Oliver, J. L., Lloyd, R. S. and Whitney, A. (2015) Monitoring of in-season neuromuscular and perceptual fatigue in youth rugby players. European Journal of Sport Science. Vol.15 (6), pp.514–522.

Pehar, M., Sisic, N., Sekulic, D., Coh, M., Uljevic, O., Spasic, M., Krolo, A. and Idrizovic, K. (2017) Analyzing the relationship between anthropometric and motor indices with basketball specific pre-planned and non-planned agility performances. The Journal of Sports

Medicine and Physical Fitness. [Online] Vol.58 (7–8), pp.1037–1044. Available: <https://europepmc.org/article/med/28488829> [Accessed 30 Oct 2023].

Pérez-Castilla, A., Fernandes, J. F. T., Rojas, F. J. and García-Ramos, A. (2021) Reliability and Magnitude of Countermovement Jump Performance Variables: Influence of the Take-off Threshold. Measurement in Physical Education and Exercise Science. [Online] Vol.25 (3), pp.227–235. Available: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/1091367X.2021.1872578> [Accessed 27 Nov 2023].

Pinto, B. L. and Callaghan, J. P. (2021) An Appropriate Criterion Reveals that Low Pass Filtering Can Improve the Estimation of Counter-movement Jump Height from Force Plate Data. Measurement in Physical Education and Exercise Science. [Online] Vol.25 (4), pp.344–352. Available: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/1091367X.2021.1906253> [Accessed 27 Nov 2023].

Portney, L. and Watkins, M. (2009) Foundations of clinical research: applications to practice [Online]. Available: <http://babymariam.gm/sites/default/files/webform/pdf-foundations-of-clinical-research-applications-to-practice-3rd-e-leslie-g-portney-mary-p-watkins-pdf-download-free-book-d3094a3.pdf> [Accessed 7 Aug 2023].

Rabita, G., Dorel, S., Slawinski, J., Sàez-de-Villarreal, E., Couturier, A., Samozino, P. and Morin, J. B. (2015) Sprint mechanics in world-class athletes: a new insight into the limits of human locomotion. Scandinavian journal of medicine & science in sports. [Online] Vol.25 (5), pp.583–594. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/25640466/> [Accessed 27 Sep 2023].

Rago, V., Brito, J., Figueiredo, P., Carvalho, T., Fernandes, T., Fonseca, P. and Rebelo, A. (2018) Countermovement Jump Analysis Using Different Portable Devices: Implications for Field Testing. Sports. [Online] Vol.6 (3). Available: </pmc/articles/PMC6162675/> [Accessed 2 Mar 2022].

Ramirez-Campillo, R., Thapa, R. K., Afonso, J., Perez-Castilla, A., Bishop, C., Byrne, P. J. and Granacher, U. (2023) Effects of Plyometric Jump Training on the Reactive Strength Index in Healthy Individuals Across the Lifespan: A Systematic Review with Meta-analysis. Sports Medicine (Auckland, N.z.). [Online] Vol.53 (5), p.1029. Available: </pmc/articles/PMC10115703/> [Accessed 15 Dec 2023].

- Redler, L. H., Watling, J. P., Dennis, E. R., Swart, E. and Ahmad, C. S. (2016) Reliability of a field-based drop vertical jump screening test for ACL injury risk assessment. Physician and Sportsmedicine. [Online] Vol.44 (1), pp.46–52. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/286478668_Reliability_of_a_Field-Based_Drop_Vertical_Jump_Screening_Test_for_ACL_Injury_Risk_Assessment [Accessed 20 Nov 2023].
- Rice, P. E., Goodman, C. L., Capps, C. R., Triplett, N. T., Erickson, T. M. and McBride, J. M. (2017) Force- and power-time curve comparison during jumping between strength-matched male and female basketball players. European journal of sport science. [Online] Vol.17 (3), pp.286–293. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27691454/> [Accessed 3 Dec 2023].
- Robineau, J., Jouaux, T., Lacroix, M. and Babault, N. (2012) Neuromuscular fatigue induced by a 90-minute soccer game modeling. Journal of strength and conditioning research. [Online] Vol.26 (2), pp.555–562. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/22240545/> [Accessed 27 Jul 2022].
- Romagnoli, M., Sanchis-Gomar, F., Alis, R., Risso-Ballester, J., Bosio, A., Graziani, R. L. and Rampinini, E. (2016) Changes in muscle damage, inflammation, and fatigue-related parameters in young elite soccer players after a match. The Journal of sports medicine and physical fitness. Vol.56 (10), pp.1198–1205.
- Romero-Parra, N., Alfaro-Magallanes, V. M., Rael, B., Cupeiro, R., Rojo-Tirado, M. A., Benito, P. J. and Peinado, A. B. (2021) Indirect Markers of Muscle Damage Throughout the Menstrual Cycle. International journal of sports physiology and performance. [Online] Vol.16 (2), pp.190–198. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32659744/> [Accessed 27 Nov 2023].
- Rubio-Peirutén, A., García-Pinillos, F., Jaén-Carrillo, D., Cartón-Llorente, A. and Roche-Seruendo, L. E. (2021) Is There a Relationship between the Morphology of Connective Tissue and Reactivity during a Drop Jump? Influence of Sex and Athletic Performance Level. International journal of environmental research and public health. [Online] Vol.18 (4), pp.1–10. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33670566/> [Accessed 6 Dec 2023].
- Salonikidis, K. and Zafeiridis, A. (2008) The effects of plyometric, tennis-drills, and combined training on reaction, lateral and linear speed, power, and strength in novice tennis players.

- Journal of strength and conditioning research. [Online] Vol.22 (1), pp.182–191. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/18296973/> [Accessed 30 Oct 2023].
- Schleitzer, S., Wirtz, S., Julian, R. and Eils, E. (2022) Development and evaluation of an inertial measurement unit (IMU) system for jump detection and jump height estimation in beach volleyball. German Journal of Exercise and Sport Research. Vol.52 (2), pp.228–236.
- Sheppard, J. and Young, W. (2006) Agility literature review: classifications, training and testing. Journal of sports sciences. [Online] Vol.24 (9), pp.919–932. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/16882626/> [Accessed 4 Jul 2022].
- Silva, J. R., Magalhaes, J., AscensaO, A., Seabra, A. F. and Rebelo, A. N. N. (2013) Training status and match activity of professional soccer players throughout a season. Journal of strength and conditioning research. [Online] Vol.27 (1), pp.20–30. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/22344051/> [Accessed 26 Jul 2022].
- Silva, R., Clemente, F. M., González-Fernández, F. T., Bernardo, A. and Ardigò, L. P. (2021) Weekly Variations of Short-Duration Maximal Jumping Performance in Soccer Players: Exploring Relationships With Accumulated Training Load and Match Demands. Frontiers in Physiology. [Online] Vol.12, p.690353. Available: </pmc/articles/PMC8417052/> [Accessed 8 Feb 2022].
- Słomka, K. J., Sobota, G., Skowronek, T., Rzepko, M., Czarny, W. and Juras, G. (2017) Evaluation of reliability and concurrent validity of two optoelectric systems used for recording maximum vertical jumping performance versus the gold standard. Acta of Bioengineering and Biomechanics. Vol.19 (2), pp.141–147.
- Sole, S., Ramírez-Campillo, R., Andrade, D. C. and Sanchez-Sanchez, J. (2021) Plyometric jump training effects on the physical fitness of individual-sport athletes: A systematic review with meta-analysis. PeerJ. [Online] Vol.9. Available: </pmc/articles/PMC7931718/> [Accessed 15 Dec 2023].
- Spiteri, T., Cochrane, J. L., Hart, N. H., Haff, G. G. and Nimphius, S. (2013) Effect of strength on plant foot kinetics and kinematics during a change of direction task. European journal of sport science. [Online] Vol.13 (6), pp.646–652. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24251742/> [Accessed 3 Jul 2022].
- Spiteri, T., Newton, R. U., Binetti, M., Hart, N. H., Sheppard, J. M. and Nimphius, S. (2015) Mechanical Determinants of Faster Change of Direction and Agility Performance in Female

- Basketball Athletes. Journal of strength and conditioning research. [Online] Vol.29 (8), pp.2205–2214. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/25734779/> [Accessed 3 Jul 2022].
- Stanton, R., Doering, T. M., Macgregor, C., Borges, N. and Delvecchio, L. (2019) Validity of a contact mat and accelerometric system to assess countermovement jump from flight time. Measurement in Physical Education and Exercise Science. [Online] Vol.23 (1), pp.39–46. Available: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/1091367X.2018.1493593> [Accessed 22 Nov 2023].
- Street, G., McMillan, S., Board, W., Rasmussen, M. and Heneghan, J. M. (2001) Sources of Error in Determining Countermovement Jump Height with the Impulse Method. Journal of Applied Biomechanics. [Online] Vol.17 (1), pp.43–54. Available: <https://journals.humankinetics.com/view/journals/jab/17/1/article-p43.xml> [Accessed 13 Mar 2023].
- Suchomel, T. J., Nimphius, S., Bellon, C. R. and Stone, M. H. (2018) The Importance of Muscular Strength: Training Considerations. Sports medicine (Auckland, N.Z.). [Online] Vol.48 (4), pp.765–785. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29372481/> [Accessed 28 Aug 2023].
- Suchomel, T. J., Sole, C. J., Bailey, C. A., Grazer, J. L. and Beckham, G. K. (2015) A comparison of reactive strength index-modified between six U.S. Collegiate athletic teams. Journal of strength and conditioning research. [Online] Vol.29 (5), pp.1310–1316. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/25436634/> [Accessed 22 Mar 2022].
- Sweeting, A. J., Cormack, S. J., Morgan, S. and Aughey, R. J. (2017) When Is a Sprint a Sprint? A Review of the Analysis of Team-Sport Athlete Activity Profile. Frontiers in physiology. [Online] Vol.8 (JUN). Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28676767/> [Accessed 10 May 2023].
- Tampa, D. H. and Buccaneers, B. (2009) Drop Jump as an indicator of Neuromuscular fatigue in soccer players. [Online]. Available: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/320658231> [Accessed 20 Apr 2022].
- Tsolakis, C., Kostaki, E. and Vagenas, G. (2010) Anthropometric, flexibility, strength-power, and sport-specific correlates in elite fencing. Perceptual and motor skills. [Online] Vol.110 (3 Pt 2), pp.1015–1028. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/20865989/> [Accessed 30 Oct 2023].

- Turner, A. N. and Jeffreys, I. (2010) The stretch-shortening cycle: Proposed mechanisms and methods for enhancement. Strength and Conditioning Journal. [Online] Vol.32 (4), pp.87–99. Available: https://journals.lww.com/nsca-scj/Fulltext/2010/08000/The_Stretch_Shortening_Cycle__Proposed_Mechanisms.10.aspx [Accessed 24 Jun 2022].
- Turner, A. N., Marshall, G., Phillips, J., Noto, A., Buttigieg, C., Chavda, S., Downing, W., Atlay, N., Dimitriou, L. and Kilduff, L. (2016) Physical Characteristics Underpinning Repetitive Lunging in Fencing. Journal of strength and conditioning research. [Online] Vol.30 (11), pp.3134–3139. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/26950343/> [Accessed 30 Oct 2023].
- Vanrenterghem, J., De Clercq, D. and Van Cleven, P. (2001) Necessary precautions in measuring correct vertical jumping height by means of force plate measurements. Ergonomics. Vol.44 (8), pp.814–818.
- Vescovi, J. D. and Favero, T. G. (2014) Motion characteristics of women’s college soccer matches: Female Athletes in Motion (FAiM) study. International journal of sports physiology and performance. [Online] Vol.9 (3), pp.405–414. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24755966/> [Accessed 23 Jun 2022].
- Viitasalo, J. T., Luhtanen, P., Mononen, H. v., Norvapalo, K., Paavolainen, L. and Salonen, M. (1997) Photocell contact mat: A new instrument to measure contact and flight times in running. Journal of Applied Biomechanics. Vol.13 (2), pp.254–266.
- Wade, L., Needham, L., McGuigan, M. P. and Bilzon, J. L. J. (2022) Backward Double Integration is a Valid Method to Calculate Maximal and Sub-Maximal Jump Height. Journal of sports sciences. [Online] Vol.40 (10), pp.1191–1197. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35356858/> [Accessed 22 Nov 2023].
- Wank, V. and Coenning, C. (2019) On the estimation of centre of gravity height in vertical jumping. German Journal of Exercise and Sport Research. [Online] Vol.49 (4), pp.454–462. Available: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s12662-019-00581-6> [Accessed 27 Nov 2023].
- Watkins, C. M., Maunder, E., van den Tillaar, R. and Oranchuk, D. J. (2020) Concurrent validity and reliability of three ultra-portable vertical jump assessment technologies. Sensors (Switzerland). Vol.20 (24), pp.1–14.

- Wilkinson, M., Cooke, M., Murray, S., Thompson, K. G., Clair Gibson, A. S. T. and Winter, E. M. (2012) Physiological correlates of multiple-sprint ability and performance in international-standard squash players. Journal of strength and conditioning research. [Online] Vol.26 (2), pp.540–547. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/22240546/> [Accessed 30 Oct 2023].
- Wilson, J. M. and Flanagan, E. P. (2008) The role of elastic energy in activities with high force and power requirements: a brief review. Journal of strength and conditioning research. [Online] Vol.22 (5), pp.1705–1715. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/18714212/> [Accessed 23 Jun 2022].
- Wong, T. L., Huang, C. F. and Chen, P. C. (2020) Effects of Lower Extremity Muscle Fatigue on Knee Loading During a Forward Drop Jump to a Vertical Jump in Female Athletes. Journal of Human Kinetics. [Online] Vol.72 (1), p.5. Available: </pmc/articles/PMC7126241/> [Accessed 7 Feb 2022].
- Xu, J., Turner, A., Comfort, P., Harry, J. R., McMahon, J. J., Chavda, S. and Bishop, C. (2023) A Systematic Review of the Different Calculation Methods for Measuring Jump Height During the Countermovement and Drop Jump Tests. Sports Medicine (Auckland, N.z.). [Online] Vol.53 (5), p.1055. Available: </pmc/articles/PMC10115716/> [Accessed 15 Nov 2023].
- Young, W. B., James, ; R and Montgomery, ; I (2002a) Is muscle power related to running speed with changed of direction? Journal of Sports Medicine and Physical Fitness. Vol.42.
- Young, W. B., James, ; R and Montgomery, ; I (2002b) Is muscle power related to running speed with changed of direction? Journal of Sports Medicine and Physical Fitness. Vol.42.
- Yu, L., Altieri, C., BIRD, S. P., Corcoran, G. and Jiuxiang, G. (2021) The Importance of In-Season Strength and Power Training in Football Athletes: A Brief Review and Recommendations. International Journal of Strength and Conditioning. Vol.1 (1).

Appendices

Appendix 1.1: Concurrent set up of Optojump and Force Plates

Appendix 1.2: Participant Information Sheet provided to all participants prior to commencement of trials (continued to page 67).

Participant Information Sheet

Study title

Investigating The Validity and Reliability Of The Optojump Device During Explosive Jump Tests Compared To Force Plate Derived Data Within Elite Female Football Players

Who are we?

I am a Master of Research Student from the University of the West of Scotland. You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Ask my lead supervisor or I if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to participate.

The study

The aim of this study is to examine the reliability and validity of the optojump device at measuring jump performance during a countermovement jump (CMJ) and a drop jump (DJ).

Why have I been asked to take part?

You have been asked to participate as you are currently playing for Hamilton Academical Women's Football Club, over the age of 16, free from spine deformities and joint pain, and have had no musculoskeletal injuries for the past 6 months which have prevented you from training and exercising normally.

What will I have to do if I take part?

You will be required to attend the University of the West of Scotland Biomechanics laboratory on two separate occasions, the visits will last 20-30 minutes. These sessions will involve you performing 2 different explosive jump tests for 3 repetitions.

You will be asked wear appropriate clothing and remove shoes upon arrival to allow for height and body mass measures to be recorded prior to data collection. Following this, a standardised 10 minute warm up will be conducted before performing submaximal trials of both jumps.

Appendix 1.2 (continued): Participant Information Sheet provided to all participants prior to commencement of trials.

Do I have to take part?

Participation in the study is not compulsory and no negative consequences will arise at your refusal to participate. If you do decide to participate you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. If your decision to participate changes for whatever reason you are free to withdraw from the research at any time without giving reason.

What are the possible risks of taking part?

Like all exercise, there is always the possibility of injury occurring during the participation of this study. However, measures have been taken to minimise this risk including the engagement of a standardised warm up, the small number of repetitions being performed of each jump as well as adequate recovery time between trials and different jump modalities. You will be given clear instructions and given time to familiarise yourself with the jumps prior to testing sessions. An experienced member of staff will be present and supervising the entire time.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

The information we get from this study may help us to identify whether this portable device can be used within elite female footballers as an alternative to force plates. The data collected from this study will provide an indication of your jump performance during a CMJ and DJ allowing for analysis to be made on vertical jump height and reactive strength index (RSI). Two measurements which provide an insight on lower-body power and your ability to utilise the stretch shortening cycle- which within the context of football are beneficial to know.

Will my taking part in this study be kept confidential?

All information which is collected about you during the research will be kept strictly confidential. Any information about you which leaves the University will be anonymised by removing your name so that you cannot be recognised from it. All participants will be assigned a participant number and will not be referred to by name. With your agreement, the information gained on your jump performance may be discussed with the squad staff. This is to allow the squad staff to have a better understanding of your individual performance and influence the training programmes utilised throughout the season.

What if I have any concerns?

Please feel free to contact the lead supervisor involved with the study Dr Mark Sanderson or myself to discuss any questions or concerns you may have.

What will happen to the results of the research study?

On completion of the testing session, all results will be documented, analysed and discussed within university assessments. These will attempt to answer the proposed research question. All assessment pieces of work will not identify any participants. You will be able to obtain a copy of your results on request following the write up of this paper.

Appendix 1.2 (continued): Participant Information Sheet provided to all participants prior to commencement of trials.

Contact for Further Information

Supervisor: Dr. Mark Sanderson

Email: [REDACTED]

Student Researcher: Luke Murray

Email: [REDACTED]

Number: [REDACTED]

Appendix 1.3: Informed Consent Form provided to all participants prior to commencement of trials.

Written Consent Form

Title of Project: Investigating the Validity And Reliability of The Optojump Device During Explosive Jump Tests Compared To Force Plate Derived Data Within Elite Female Football Players
Name of Researcher: Luke Murray

Please Initial box

- | | | |
|---|--|--------------------------|
| 1 | I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions. | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 2 | I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason. | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 3 | I agree to share any performance data gathered from this study with the coaching team and squad. | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 4 | I agree to take part in the above study. | <input type="checkbox"/> |

Name of Participant:

Signature:

Date:

Name of person taking consent (if different from researcher):

Signature:

Date:

Name of researcher:

Signature:

Date:

Appendix 1.4: PAR-Q Form provided to all participants prior to commencement of trials (continued on to page 71).

Medical Questionnaire for Physiological Testing

Before any physiological tests are carried on you, we will have to check whether you are in a satisfactory condition to undergo strenuous exercise. We would therefore like you to fill in the following questionnaire about yourself. All information will be treated as strictly confidential.

Name _____ Date of Birth ____/____/____
Specialist Sport (if any) _____ Male Female

PLEASE TICK ONE ANSWER ONLY

1. Have you ever had a heart attack, coronary revascularisation surgery or a stroke?
No Yes
2. Has your doctor ever told you that you have heart trouble or vascular disease?
No Yes
3. Has your doctor ever told you that you have a heart murmur?
No Yes
4. Do you ever suffer from pains in your chest, especially with exercise?
No Yes
5. Do you ever get pains in your calves, buttocks or at the back of your legs during exercise which are not due to soreness or stiffness?
No Yes
6. Do you ever feel faint or have spells of severe dizziness, particularly with exercise?
No Yes
7. Do you experience swelling or accumulation of fluid about the ankles?
No Yes
8. Do you ever get the feeling that your heart is suddenly beating faster, racing or skipping beats, either at rest or during exercise?
No Yes
9. Do you have chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, interstitial lung disease, or cystic fibrosis?
No Yes
10. Have you ever had an attack of shortness of breath that developed when you were not doing anything strenuous, at any time in the last 12 months?
No Yes

Appendix 1.4 (continued): PAR-Q Form provided to all participants prior to commencement of trials.

11. Have you ever had an attack of shortness of breath that developed after you stopped exercising, at any time in the last 12 months?

No Yes

12. Have you ever been woken at night by an attack of shortness of breath, at any time in the last 12 months?

No Yes

13. Do you have diabetes [Type I (Insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus (IDDM)) or Type II (non-insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus (NIDDM))]? If so, do you have trouble controlling your diabetes?

No Yes

14. Do you have any ulcerated wounds or cuts on your feet that do not seem to heal?

No Yes

15. Do you have any liver, kidney or thyroid disorders?

No Yes

16. Do you experience unusual fatigue or shortness of breath with usual activities?

No Yes

17. Is there any other physical reason or medical condition, or are you taking any medication(s) which could prevent you from undertaking an exercise program, or that you are concerned about? If so, please explain. *(see notes)

No Yes

18. Have you ever suffered from a viral infection in the last two weeks?

No Yes

* NOTES: Some of these conditions might include a history of blood clotting, osteoporosis, bone fractures or serious musculoskeletal disorders, or if they have recently lost a weight without trying to. Other types of conditions might include psychiatric disorders, later-stage pregnancy or those with a history of health problems during pregnancy. Those people taking medication(s) for medical conditions listed may also need medical clearance.

I have read, understood and completed this questionnaire. Any questions I had were answered to my full satisfaction. If there will be a change of status to any of the conditions above I will inform the researcher or the senior academic involved IMMEDIATELY.

NAME _____ SIGNATURE _____ DATE ____/____/____

Appendix 1.4 (continued): PAR-Q Form provided to all participants prior to commencement of trials.

References: (1) Sports Medicine Australia (SMA) pre-exercise screening system 2003, Australian Government, Department of Health and Ageing (2) American College of Sports Medicine (ACSM) (2000). ACSM's guidelines for exercise testing and prescription (6th ed). New York, Lippincott Williams & Wilkins. (3) Australian Institute of Health and Welfare (AIHW) (2004). Heart, stroke and vascular diseases Australian facts 2004. Canberra, AIHW and National Heart Foundation of Australia. (4) National Heart Foundation (NHF) (2005). Physical activity recommendations for people with cardiovascular disease. Sydney, National Heart Foundation of Australia. (5) Olds, T. and Norton, K. (1999). Pre-exercise health screening guide. Champaign, IL, Human Kinetics.

UWS Sport and Exercise Laboratories Screening Flow Chart

To be completed by test supervisor:	
<u>MUST BE SIGNED BEFORE THE SUBJECT STARTS EXERCISE</u>	
Checked by _____	Signed _____
Date ____/____/____	